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ABSTRACT

Due to a rapidly evolving and emerging knowledge economy, organizations today face several difficulties and challenges. Businesses worldwide must improve operations to establish a sustainable competitive advantage and guarantee growth. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), with knowledge creation as their pinnacle of business, face the greatest challenge of strategically positioning themselves to be responsive to the new demands of the knowledge economy. Universities are the primary formal means of producing, distributing, and transferring knowledge—crucial for expanding the global economy—. Educational leaders must support innovations to accomplish organizational goals effectively and efficiently and maintain their position as industry leaders. This study assessed the Key Factors of Knowledge Management (KM) Practices, KM Process, and KM Performance Outcomes of a Private University System in the Philippines. Specifically, this study determined the level of performance of KM Practices in terms of Organizational Culture, Information Technology (IT), and Employee Motivation; assessed the KM Process in terms of Knowledge Generation, Knowledge Storage, Knowledge Sharing, and Knowledge Application; determined the KM Performance Outcome levels in terms of Teaching, Research, and International Outlook; tested the significant relationships between KM Practices and KM Process; to KM Performance Outcomes; and developed a KM Model for a private university system. A descriptive research design was used in this study and utilized purposive random sampling techniques with two hundred thirty-six faculty members of a private university system in the Philippines. The study revealed a high level of assessment of implementing the Key Factors of KM Practices in the university system regarding Organizational Culture, Information Technology, and Employee Motivation. Generally, all stages of the KM Process are always practiced in the university system. However, an intensified implementation of the activities under the Knowledge Application and Storage stages is needed. A moderate level of assessment of the Performance Outcomes of KM implementation in Teaching, Research, and International Outlook was also revealed in this study. Furthermore, the study revealed strong and significant relationships between Key Factors of KM Practices and KM Processes to KM Performance Outcomes.

Keywords: *Knowledge management, practices, process, performance outcomes, higher education institutions*

INTRODUCTION

Due to rapid changes in a modern and new knowledge economy, enterprises worldwide face a global problem. The challenge for businesses is to enhance their operations for a sustainable competitive edge and growth. In the present knowledge economy, knowledge is recognized as the primary economic and strategic resource and a tool for attaining competitive advantage for organizations. (Prelipcean, 2016). The new competitive advantage in business is knowledge, as firms no longer compete primarily on financial capital and strength (Omotayo, 2015). Knowledge is the most valuable resource in this digital age. Knowledge has replaced money, natural resources, and labor as essential economic resources (Khan, 2014). To deal with the shifting demands and expectations of the company, many organizations throughout the world have adopted and accepted Knowledge Management (KM) as a management paradigm.

Today, managing information is the issue rather than finding it. The most pressing task for enterprises is how to process knowledge and make it valuable in the contemporary knowledge-driven economy. Due to this difficulty, organizations anticipate that KM will be an essential element in determining an organization's effectiveness, along with organizational culture, structure, and strategy.

The most important topics have been covered in works that have concentrated on introducing knowledge management in the organization so that the system may be used successfully. Organizations tend to focus on the creation, sharing, and protection of knowledge, as well as on continuous learning within the organizations, understanding the organization as a whole system, creating an innovative culture to support Research and Development (R&D) initiatives, individualized approaches, and competence development and management based on competencies. According to Ismail et al. (2016), organizational culture, information technology (IT), and motivation are three (3) of the most crucial factors to consider while implementing knowledge management. It not only helps to link people, but it also positively affects KM processes and practices (Che Pa et al., 2012). These variables serve as the

dimensions of KM practices in this study. Additionally, KM improves organizational performance (Ahmed et al., 2015) and offers long-lasting competitive benefits in innovation, product improvement, and employee improvement (Chou et al., 2015; Dickel et al., 2016).

Furthermore, according to Heisig (2009), the KM process encompasses organizational actions that control the flow of knowledge inside an organization. According to Turner et al. (2012), knowledge management consists of four(4) main stages: knowledge creation or knowledge generation, which calls for organizations to look for new knowledge and information both inside and outside of the organizations; knowledge storage to make knowledge available for easier accessibility; and knowledge transfer to share and exchange knowledge among individuals or networks of individuals as well as knowledge application, in which businesses use knowledge to alter their strategic directions, solve problems, make decisions, increase efficiency, and cut expenses. Without having to study it themselves, the person can utilize the information that others have (Hegazy et al., 2014).

Higher educational institutions (HEIs), whose core competency is knowledge creation, need help positioning themselves strategically to meet the evolving demands of the knowledge economy (Bitera, 2022). Universities are the primary formal medium for producing, disseminating, and transferring knowledge, which is essential for the expansion of the global economy (Trivella et al., 2015). Therefore, to accomplish their organizational goals effectively and efficiently and maintain their position as industry leaders, educational leaders must support innovations (Bitera, 2022). The corporate environment and economy are rapidly changing, and this also impacts the educational sector (Zwain et al., 2012). HEIs are expected to manage knowledge for long-term competitive advantage, growth, and innovation as knowledge-based organizations (Ohiorenoya et al., 2014). The implementation of KM in HEIs will have numerous immediate benefits for academic achievements because of its enormous benefits for HEIs that focus on the research process, curriculum creation process, student and alumni services, administrative services, and strategic business planning. In a university system with numerous geographically dispersed campuses, each campus has a distinctive name and administrative structure. A university system should be an organized academic body made up of various but linked units, at least one of which is at the university level, according to the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). An institution of higher learning has its system administration coordinated and integrated by a board's chief executive officer/chairman.

As knowledge-based institutions, HEIs' primary competitive advantage is their capacity to manage knowledge, a dynamic process that has proven difficult yet advantageous for all parties involved. Universities work to establish their competitive edge in the face of a dynamic and competitive HEI landscape by focusing their efforts on three (3) areas: teaching and learning, research, and business enterprise activities (Elezi, 2021). Unquestionably, teaching and learning are crucial to performing a university's core duties and accounting for most of the institution's revenue (Universities UK, 2016).

HEIs have traditionally taken part in KM activities. According to Fullwood et al. (2013) and Ramachandran et al. (2013), the three (3) purposes of universities—research, education, and service to society—are intertwined with knowledge generation, dissemination, and transfer, respectively. These activities, in turn, align with the steps in the knowledge management (KM) process that deal with knowledge production, storage, sharing, and application. In HEIs, academicians are acknowledged as knowledge workers who produce, consume, share, and apply that knowledge across the institution. Therefore, HEIs must create strategies that use academicians' information to gain competitive advantages and improve their performances (Devi et al., 2013; Popescu, 2017; Trivella et al., 2015).

Research gaps must be filled, notwithstanding KM's rising popularity and pivotal adoption in some HEIs in the Philippines. According to Kulkarni et al. (2013), more research and development must be done in this field to benefit from KM fully. The definition of KM in various contexts has only been made clear in a few extant research investigations. An established and even a basic concept of a KM system is only sometimes. More empirical evaluation of KM practices and enablers in HEIs is becoming increasingly necessary, particularly in a complex and unstable environment (Almudallal et al., 2016), even though KM is an innovative instrument providing a durable advantage (Serenko, 2013).

Lack of adequate KM operationalization, understanding, and identification of organizational knowledge are significant concerns for Philippine HEIs. Although the stages of the KM process are being used, they have yet to be fully defined and implemented. Furthermore, it can be challenging to incorporate KM into HEIs' primary operations. In contrast to research, there is no statutory and legislated policy governing the integration of KM into the operations of HEIs (Bitera, 2022). The application of KM practices as a component of KPIs to support International Organization for Standardization (ISO) certification and accreditation standards now faces a new hurdle.

The researcher has been fascinated with the scope and context of KM as a new subject under the Doctor of Philosophy in Management program. As an educator and a marketing practitioner, the

researcher would like to know and understand how an educational institution, as an academic center, facilitates the creation, sharing, storage, and application of knowledge and how these impact the overall organizational performance. The researcher would also like to know if KM is included in the strategic plan of the university system being studied or if the university system follows an existing model. Since the start of the researcher's employment at the university, the researcher has yet to be aware of a KM Model being utilized by the university. The various Quality Assurance mechanisms of the university system, such as Quacquarelli Symonds (QS) World University Rankings: Asia and QS Stars rating, Philippine Quality Award (PQA), CHED's Institutional Sustainability Assessment (ISA), ASEAN University Network - Quality Assurance (AUN-QA), and Knowledge Management Systems - Standards (ISO 30401:2018) enjoin each organization to craft its own KM solution, reflecting its specific needs and situation and produce valuable results derived from applied knowledge. With this pressing importance, the researcher wishes to share inputs on how the university system can improve its KM practices and process and create its own KM Model to standardize this management field. On a personal level, this will also help the researcher on how to effectively manage the knowledge that he has and will have as a knowledge worker and how to share this with other knowledge workers effectively.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The study utilized a descriptive research design for an adequate and precise interpretation of the findings. All research, including surveys and co-relational studies, that aims to give information about the nature and status of anything falls under this methodology. Descriptive research, as defined by Atmowardoyo (2018), is a type of study in which existent occurrences are described as accurately as feasible. The phenomena that descriptive research identifies are already known. A researcher must first gather the already available data utilizing tests, questionnaires, interviews, and even observation. The primary objective of descriptive research is to characterize the studied phenomena thoroughly.

Respondents. In this study, the respondents were the faculty members of a private university system in the Philippines. Specifically, this study used purposive, stratified, quota, and random sampling techniques. Purposive sampling was used in selecting the private university system in the Philippines. Furthermore, stratified, quota, and random sampling were used in selecting the faculty members in each campus of the identified university system. The faculty members were chosen since, as academic centers for KM, universities, as mandated by its tri-fold function on instruction, research, and community extension, are expected to implement Knowledge Management as a way of life. The faculty members were between 20 to 60 years old and above, with bachelor's and postgraduate degrees, and have been in the university system from 5 years to 20 years and above. The faculty members were from all the programs offered by the university system, including but not limited to high school, business, culinary, tourism, hospitality management, engineering, medical, education, graduate studies, maritime, psychology, and criminal justice. The researcher used RAOSOFT and based the computed sample on the total population of 825 faculty members and a 99% confidence level with a 0.50 response distribution at a 1% margin of error; 236 were obtained. The total number of faculty members needed was proportionately divided in each campus using stratified sampling.

Data Collection Procedure. Before the researcher came up with the final research proposal, the researcher did an advanced reading about the topic chosen. Related variables, dimensions, and indicators were reviewed before developing the proposed research title. Then, the researcher sought the suggestions of the research teacher on how further to enhance the components of the proposed research title. The research proposal was presented virtually in front of a group of panelists who raised their suggestions for improving the study and finally gave a signal to conduct it.

Moreover, this study adapted a research instrument from a related study. Moreso, the researcher sought the approval of the referent researcher through email to use his instrument for this study. After the approval of the referent researcher to use the instrument, the researcher conducted a thorough review of the instrument and made necessary alignments and adjustments.

After content validation, a pilot testing of the validated instrument was conducted. The instrument was distributed, online and in-person, to some sample members using convenience sampling. Receiving no responses from other campuses after weeks of requests, the researcher conducted a pilot test in one campus only in consultation with the adviser, expert, and statistician. After the pilot test, gathered data were encoded, tabulated, cleaned, and forwarded to the statistician for a reliability test. The reliability test result showed promising results having "excellent" marks for the

majority of the dimensions. Then, actual data gathering followed. An endorsement was sought from the University Presidents of the three identified campuses and was forwarded to all the concerned departments of all the campuses. The research instrument was made available in a physical copy and as an online form which was accessible anytime and anywhere. Retrieval of distributed research instruments, in person and online, followed. 100% of the required responses were gathered. After all, data were completed and gathered, and it was collated, tabulated, tallied, and cleaned for statistical treatment and interpretation. Analysis of data followed.

Data Analysis Procedure. The needed data were tallied, encoded, and analyzed using statistical tools and measures. Central Tendency (weighted mean) was used to assess and evaluate the levels of KM Practices on KM Key Factors in terms of Organizational Culture, Information Technology (IT), and Employee Motivation; KM Process in terms of Knowledge Generation, Knowledge Storage, Knowledge Sharing, and Knowledge Application; and KM Performance Outcomes in terms of Teaching, Research, and International Outlook.

To determine the relationship and linear association between or among the variables KM Practices on KM Key Factors and KM Process; and KM Process on KM Performance Outcomes, Pearson r (for parametric data), Kendall's tau β and Spearman's rho, and Chi-square (for non-parametric data) were used. All gathered data were treated using statistical software to interpret the study results further.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the demographic profiles of the faculty members. In terms of the campus where they are currently employed as faculty members, 34.7% of the respondents are from LPU-Cavite (Campus 1), 26.3% are from LPU-Batangas (Campus 2) followed by LPU-Manila/Makati (Campus 3) with 20.8%, 16.5% from LPU-Laguna (Campus 4) and 1.7% from LPU-Davao (Campus 5). The proportionate distribution of the faculty members needed as respondents corresponded to the number of faculty members employed on each campus. This means that all data gathered well represent the viewpoints and perceptions of the members of the population on the variables presented.

As to age, 34.7% of the faculty members are in the 20-year to 30-year-old bracket, 27.5% are between 31 to 40 years old, 23.7% are between 41 to 50, and 14% are above 51 years old. The data imply that the university system employs a diverse workforce across different generations. This diversity in faculty members is valuable to determine how Knowledge Management is being perceived and received by them and will help determine programs that apply to everyone.

In terms of gender, 54.2% of the faculty members are female, while 45.8% of the faculty members are male. This implies that the data gathered represent well the viewpoints of both female and male faculty members of LPU campuses on the research topic.

For qualifications, 52.5% of the faculty members are master's degree holders, 28% holds bachelor's degree, and 19.5% are Ph.D. holders. This shows that as purveyors of knowledge, faculty members are eager to further their educational attainment by getting postgraduate degrees, which is vital in implementing Knowledge Management initiatives and programs.

In terms of the areas of specialization, most of the faculty members, which is 27.1%, are inclined to the field of education. Sharing an equal distribution percentage of 23.3% are the areas of Culinary, Tourism, Hospitality Management, and Business Management. At the same time, the rest of the respondents are experts in Engineering, Criminology, Medicine, Psychology, and Maritime. These fields are the university system's flagship programs, which means that the teaching force comprises experts from these fields.

In terms of tenure ship, 37.7% of the faculty members have been employed in the university system for five years and below, 32.2% have been with the institution for six to 10 years, 14.8% is with the institution for 15 to twenty (20) years while 7.2% has been teaching in the institution for more than 20 years. The data are instrumental in determining the implementation of the research topic in each campus, at least in the past two decades.

Table 1. Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Faculty Members

Campus	Frequency	Percentage %
Campus 1	49	20.8
Campus 2	62	26.3
Campus 3	82	34.7
Campus 4	39	16.5
Campus 5	4	1.7
Age		
20 – 30 years old	82	34.7
31 – 40 years old	65	27.5
41 – 50 years old	56	23.7
51 – 60 years old	21	8.9
61 years old and above	12	5.1
Gender		
Male	108	45.8
Female	128	54.2
Qualifications		
Bachelor's Degree	66	28.0
With Masters	124	52.5
PhD Holder	46	19.5
Area of Specialization		
Education	64	27.1
Culinary, Tourism, and Hospitality Management	55	23.3
Business Management	55	23.3
Engineering	25	10.6
Criminology	9	3.8
Medicine	16	6.8
Psychology	11	4.7
Maritime	1	.4
Tenure		
Five years and below	89	37.7
6 – 10	76	32.2
11 – 15	35	14.8
15 – 20	19	8.1
20 years and above	17	7.2

Table 2 presents the faculty member's assessment of the Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in terms of Organizational Culture. With a composite mean of 4.56, faculty members agreed that the indicators are always practiced on their campuses. Nine (9) out of ten (10) indicators got an "always" verbal interpretation, implying that they are constantly being practiced in the university system.

The university controls the use of information in line with regulatory and compliance requirements, ranked 1st, and got the highest weighted mean of 4.65. This implies that every campus has placed controls on information usage and sharing. In an interview conducted with the Quality Assurance representative of one of the campuses, the interviewee stated that in compliance with the requirements and provisions of the accrediting body, specifically the Certification International (CI) for International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the university needed to set controls on how the

organization disseminates and use data, information, and knowledge; and these controls are being cascaded to all the members of the university. The university follows the Control of Documented Information procedure wherein the university defines the authorized copyholders or intended recipients of the controlled document. Other measures include controlling documents, forms, and records of the university.

Furthermore, according to the Data Privacy Officer of the same university, strict compliance with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012 is being observed; various awareness programs and projects are being conducted for all stakeholders. Such programs include awareness campaigns, webinars and training, and information sessions. Ilfinedo (2014) claims that adhering to corporate information security policies and processes is an excellent way to reduce business information security breaches.

The university incorporates knowledge sharing in training and developmental activities and got the second-highest weighted mean of 4.64. This implies that as an educational institution, knowledge, and knowledge sharing are at the core of its mission, and the respective managements provide avenues for the faculty members to share their knowledge during academic gatherings and sessions. In an interview with the HR Deputy Director of one of the campuses, the Deputy Director confirmed that various trainings, seminars, webinars, symposia, and conferences are being held to serve as a venue for the exchange of ideas and knowledge sharing among the faculty members. To encourage and support the application of knowledge management in enterprises, Zhang et al. (2017) found that coworkers who participate in information-sharing activities like training, development programs, and the like exhibit greater agreeableness and extraversion orientation at work. Employees tend to communicate large amounts of practical information inside an organization, which boosts their organizational embeddedness and influence (Henttonen et al., 2016) and makes them a prominent and sought-after source of knowledge (Cross et al., 2013).

Garnering an equal-weighted mean of 4.63 and ranking 3rd among the indicators, the university considers KM the center of the organization's overall strategy in achieving its vision and mission; and facilitates knowledge sharing. These signify that faculty members notice the actions and decisions of the management in integrating knowledge management into the vision and mission of their respective campuses. The result is affirmed by the study conducted by AL-Hakim et al. (2012), stating that many Malaysian educational institutions want better ways to convert knowledge into effective decision-making and action plans. As a result, higher education institutions place a strong emphasis on making individual knowledge applicable to the accomplishment of their missions. Institutions of higher learning must manage the procedures involved in producing knowledge and creativity through shared ideas to fulfill their institutional purposes, which include education, research, and service to society. Reexamining the organization's vision, values, and business goals to implement an organizational development intervention explicitly tailored for the knowledge management system is one of the processes in developing a knowledge management strategy for a company, according to Sokoh et al. (2021). The result is also consistent with research by Alsaadi (2018) and Rivera et al. (2016), which found that information sharing is routinely and constantly conducted in higher education institutions in Saudi Arabia and a Mexican university.

Other indicators that got high assessments from the faculty members are the university disseminates knowledge effectively through a set of procedures and formal networks with 4.59 weighted mean (rank 5); the university acknowledges student value creation as a significant objective of KM posted a 4.57 weighted mean (rank 6); supports the continual development of creative thinking skills of its faculty and staff with 4.53 weighted mean (rank 7); and ensures that its faculty and staff have a general understanding of knowledge management got a weighted mean of 4.50 (rank 8).

The university provides its faculty and staff immediate feedback to help their own learning, ranked 9th among the ten (10) indicators, yet got a high assessment of 4.46 weighted mean. This implies that feedback mechanisms are available and being conducted within the university system; however, delays in the results of these feedback mechanisms are prevalent. The study conducted by Gu et al. (2023) pointed out that real-time performance feedback systems assist staff in resolving process and performance irregularities, which lowers volatility in logistics, information sharing, and cash flows. Employees are frequently given performance feedback to let them know how they are doing in comparison to benchmarks like goals, targets, and peer performance (Erickson et al., 2021). Individual employees purposefully and proactively seek feedback to get ready for what they will hear in their performance reviews or to learn how others perceive them because they are inherently and genuinely interested in how they are doing and whether they are on the right track (Lee et al., 2021). Therefore, management must give workers timely feedback so they can improve and modify how they carry out their duties, especially in learning business.

The table also presents a moderate level of assessment on the university system's allocation of sufficient funding for knowledge management initiatives which ranked 10th, with a weighted mean of 4.38, interpreted as "often." This implies that despite the presence of KM practices and processes in the university system, it is not the management's priority in budget allocation. In an interview with the Quality Assurance representative of one of the campuses, the interviewee stated that the university had allocated a good amount of budget for the initial implementation of KM this semester and has yet to allocate a substantial amount of budget for Knowledge Management for the next academic year since it is a requirement of different quality assurance programs such as QS World University rankings-Asia, EOMS-ISO 21001:2018, PACUCOA Accreditation, among others. According to Shao et al. (2012), top management's support has been shown to help technical implementations succeed. Since KM uses technology and information systems, top management must fully support it. Top management support and appropriate employee incentive structures facilitate and encourage knowledge sharing, which may contribute to organizational performance (Lee et al., 2016). The senior management is often in charge of establishing the vision and is prepared to devote significant resources to attempts to implement knowledge sharing (Sulayman et al., 2012).

Table 4. Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in Terms of Organizational Culture

Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in Terms of Organizational Culture	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Knowledge management is the center of the organization's overall strategy for achieving its vision and mission.	4.63	Always	3.5
2. Incorporates knowledge sharing in training and developmental activities.	4.64	Always	2
3. Facilitates knowledge sharing.	4.63	Always	3.5
4. Disseminates knowledge effectively through set procedures and formal networks.	4.59	Always	5
5. Controls the use of information in line with regulatory and compliance requirements.	4.65	Always	1
6. Allocates sufficient budget for knowledge management initiatives.	4.38	Often	10
7. Ensures that its faculty and staff have a general understanding of knowledge management.	4.50	Always	8
8. Supports the continual development of creative thinking skills of its faculty and staff.	4.53	Always	7
9. Provides its faculty and staff immediate feedback to help their learning.	4.46	Always	9
10. Acknowledges student value creation as a major objective of knowledge management.	4.57	Always	6
Composite Mean	4.56	Always	

Table 3 presents the faculty member's assessment of the Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in Information Technology. With a composite mean of 4.61, faculty members agreed that the indicators are always practiced on their respective campuses.

Sharing the highest and equal-weighted mean of 4.67, key experts manage the university's Information Technology, have security protocols for data and knowledge management, and have a secured database. This means that a specific work unit to manage information technology and other related systems exists in the university system and is managed by experts in these fields. These work units also have set controls and measures on how all university system members will utilize data, information, and knowledge. The data provided by the HR Department of one of the campuses explicitly presented the qualifications of the current Management Information Systems Department team members. The team comprises IT experts, computer programmers, systems engineers, and software engineers. Most of the staff possess long years of work experience and postgraduate degrees. According to Ellwood et al. (2022), bringing in business-unit expertise should be expected to close knowledge gaps compared to solely technical teams, such as the market understanding needed to push innovation and knowledge management projects through the valley of death. Information technology management, a crucial component of the knowledge infrastructure, must therefore be done by professionals who possess both technical and creative talents. According to Gourova (2013), significant emphasis should be given to individuals and experts with the necessary skills and competencies, the right KM tools and organizational architecture, knowledge subjects and structures, and ICT tools and systems supporting KM. These are necessary components for KM success in a university setting. The results, however, are in direct opposition to the findings of the study by Jennex et al. (2014), which found that most companies view knowledge as an asset. They also suggest that these organizations are not worried about losing or potentially damaging the knowledge they have created, so neither a knowledge security framework nor a contingency plan has been put in place. Furthermore, the findings align with a study by Yang et al. (2012), which found that the success of projects involving knowledge management practice depends on using sophisticated IT tools such as database management systems and data and knowledge management methodologies.

Other indicators also posted a high assessment from the faculty members. The university's IT links all members to one another; and is designed to help employees work more efficiently, shared an equal-weighted mean of 4.61, and ranked ^{fourth}. The university's IT is designed to help employees make data-driven decisions, ranked 6th and posted a weighted mean of 4.60; has a data warehouse that is accessible; and is continuously upgraded, garnered a rating of 4.58 and both ranked 7th among all indicators.

The university's IT links all members to the stakeholders and reaches appropriate decision-makers in a timely fashion or as needed. It got the lowest weighted mean of 4.54 yet was verbally interpreted as always practiced in the university system. This means that the in-place IT systems and practices assist the faculty members and the university system in decision-making. Though both indicators ranked as the two lowest rated indicators, both are still being practiced "always" in the university system. The scope of responsibility granted to faculty members regarding decision-making using stakeholders' data still needs to be well structured. This contrasts with the findings of a study by Zaquot et al. (2018) on the use of IT and its impact on the involvement of staff in decision-making at Palestinian universities, which found significant significance and a positive link. This contrasts with the findings of a study on learning organizations and their role in organizational excellence in Palestinian universities done by Al Shobaki et al. (2017), wherein the availability of IT aids in timely decision-making and received a large portion of approval and evaluation from the respondents. This also goes against the findings of a study by Patil (2016), which found that ICT implementations in different business schools in the Pune Region were highly successful in connecting and collaborating via ICT systems.

Table 3. Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in Terms of Information Technology

Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in Terms of Information Technology	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. links all members to one another.	4.61	Always	4.5
2. links all members to the stakeholders.	4.54	Always	10
3. has a database that is secured.	4.67	Always	1.5
4. has a data warehouse that is accessible.	4.58	Always	7.5
5. is being managed by key experts.	4.67	Always	1.5
6. is designed to help employees work more efficiently.	4.61	Always	4.5
7. is designed to help employees make data-driven decisions.	4.60	Always	6
8. reaches appropriate decision-makers in a timely fashion or as needed.	4.54	Always	10
9. has in place security protocols for data and knowledge management.	4.67	Always	1.5
10. is continuously upgraded.	4.58	Always	7.5
Composite Mean	4.61	Always	

Table 4 presents the faculty member's assessment of the Knowledge Management Practices in terms of Employee Motivation, posting a composite mean of 4.21, implying that all indicators are being practiced often in the university system. No indicator posted a weighted mean higher than 4.49, which means that practices are present. However, the weight of priority in terms of implementation is at a moderate level. This result supports a study by Fiscal (2019) in which faculty members from state colleges in the Philippines likewise gave employee motivating techniques a moderate rating. Sunalai (2015) asserts that managers should use incentive and reward programs to spread KM ideals. According to Chumjit (2012) and Tan et al. (2013), motivation and reward systems can be either monetary (bonuses and incentives) or non-financial (recognition and advancement).

The university has developed a specific set of indicators and processes to manage knowledge, ranked 1st, and posted the highest weighted mean of 4.34. This implies that there are a set of processes in place for knowledge management, however, with a low level of implementation. In an interview with a Quality Assurance representative, the interviewee mentioned that processes and practices to manage knowledge properly are being practiced by the HR, Library, and Research Departments. These departments oversee facilitating knowledge sharing, transfer, and storage. Moreover, repositories and archives are available to store explicit knowledge from various knowledge-sharing sessions. The HR Department is also utilizing an explicit procedure for transferring organizational knowledge. According to Omatoyo (2015), a crucial KM practice is the establishment of knowledge repositories that house databases of codified knowledge assets that are logically arranged to aid searching, browsing, and retrieval. Lessons learned from best practices, planning documents, project proposals, marketing presentations, may be found in knowledge repositories. Knowledge repositories also serve as an organization's memory, storing information integrated into a system, such as customs, past events, business procedures, and human knowledge (Fadhlan et al., 2022).

The university allocates resources toward efforts that measurably increase its knowledge base, which was the second most often employee motivation indicator practiced in the organization with a weighted mean of 4.31. The moderate level of assessment implies the faculty member's awareness that there are, but not enough resources allocated to KM practices implementation. According to the study by Ajayi et al. (2021), knowledge management in Nigerian institutions can only continue to achieve its

goals if adequate financial resources are allocated. Some of the necessary knowledge management systems that could transform tacit information into explicit knowledge must be implemented at a significant cost (Hasanali, 2012).

The table shows that all indicators are often practiced within the university system. The university has a system to measure intangible assets (intellectual capital) ranked 3rd and posted a 4.25 weighted mean; rewards intellectual capital in the organization ranked 4th with a 4.23 weighted mean; links knowledge management to budget allocation also ranked 4th with a 4.23 weighted mean; utilizes an assessment mechanism of how knowledge capital contributes to rank-and-file use; and praises faculty and staff for their exemplary works in Knowledge Management through an established KM reward system both ranked 6th with 4.22 weighted mean; provides faculty and staff increased job security for sharing their knowledge ranked 8th with a weighted mean of 4.16. This moderate level of assessment implies that the management needs to develop a strong incentives and rewards system for Knowledge Management that will motivate the employees to contribute to developing a more mature knowledge culture. The result is affirmed by the study conducted by Nhung et al. (2020) for a low rating for incentives and reward systems on KM among lecturers in academic institutions in Vietnam. Employee motivation and senior management support are two critical characteristics that Moffett et al. (2012) found in their study essential to effective knowledge management. Since the reward system is the most effective driver of knowledge sharing, Loan et al. (2020) study recommended that universities offer appropriate reward programs to foster knowledge sharing among academics.

The university gives faculty, and staff increased promotion opportunities for sharing their knowledge, ranked 9th among the ten (10) indicators presented with a weighted mean of 4.11. This implies that a low level of opportunities for promotion is present in the university system for sharing knowledge. This result is affirmed through an interview with the HR Deputy Director of one of the campuses that knowledge-sharing involvement is a part of the criteria for performance evaluation and employee promotion; however, it is not the main basis for promotion. The low ratings were also affirmed by the study of Jahani et al. (2013), which presented that implicit and explicit knowledge-sharing, two categories of knowledge-sharing behavior, did not significantly correlate with extrinsic reward. Sharing tacit information requires intrinsic rewards, such as improved status, repute, and reputation.

The university grants faculty and staff higher performance-based bonuses for sharing their knowledge was the least rated indicator with a 4.02 weighted mean. This implies that this practice is present, however, not a major criterion for granting performance-based rewards. This was affirmed by the interview with the HR Deputy Director of one of the campuses that this practice is not part of the criterion for performance-based employee rewards. Kawedar et al. (2015) revealed that providing employees compensation through a performance bonus may encourage them to impart their knowledge while doing their job. Employees may thus be willing to share their knowledge if they see the clear advantages of doing so.

Table 4. Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in Terms of Employee Motivation

Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices in Terms of Employee Motivation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. rewards intellectual capital in the organization.	4.23	Often	4
2. utilizes an assessment mechanism of how knowledge capital contributes to rank-and-file use.	4.22	Often	6.5
3. has developed a specific set of indicators and processes to manage knowledge.	4.34	Often	1
4. has a system to measure intangible assets (intellectual capital).	4.25	Often	3
5. links knowledge management to budget allocation.	4.23	Often	4
6. allocates resources toward efforts that measurably increase its knowledge base.	4.31	Often	2
7. praises faculty and staff for their exemplary work in Knowledge Management through an established KM reward system.	4.22	Often	6.5
8. gives faculty and staff increased promotion opportunities for sharing their knowledge.	4.11	Often	9
9. provides faculty and staff with increased job security for sharing their knowledge.	4.16	Often	8
10. grants faculty and staff higher performance-based bonuses for sharing their knowledge.	4.02	Often	10
Composite Mean	4.21	Often	

Table 5 presents the grand composite mean of all three (3) Key factors of KM Practices of the university system, which is 4.46 verbally interpreted as always practiced in the university system. Information Technology obtained the highest composite mean of 4.61, followed by Organizational Culture (4.56), then Employee Motivation (4.21). This implies that the three (3) key factors are always being experienced and practiced by the faculty members in the university system. The result is consistent with the study conducted by Fiscal (2019) and Fiscal (2021) that organizational culture, leadership, information technology, and employee motivation practices on KM were often experienced by the faculty and staff in state universities in the Philippines. Moreover, Yang et al. (2012) affirmed that knowledge management is significantly improved by using information technology solutions. This, however, contradicts research by Rivera et al. (2016) that found IT to be the least important knowledge management enabler and to have frequently been overstated. The development, storage, and transfer of information throughout departments are all examples of knowledge management strategies that have been proven to be highly successful, according to Lam et al. (2021). According to Ismail et al. (2016), organizational culture benefits how well KM performs within the organization. The study by Rivera et al. (2016), which found that corporate culture is seen as the most important enabler of knowledge management, further supported this. According to Hislop (2013), HRM strategies can influence employees' attitudes toward and engagement in KM activities. Making the correct incentives for employees to share and apply knowledge is one of the most crucial difficulties while working in knowledge management, according to Olatukon et al. (2012). Employees' motivation and compensation

must complement the knowledge-sharing culture (Omatoyo, 2015). The result is also consistent with a study by Rivera et al. (2016). The latter portion of knowledge management enablers includes HR practices regarding the reward system.

Table 5. Summary Table on Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices

Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Organizational Culture	4.56	Always	2
2. Information Technology	4.61	Always	1
3. Employee Motivation	4.21	Always	3
Grand Composite Mean	4.46	Always	

Table 6 presents the level of faculty member's assessment of the organization's application of the Knowledge Management process in terms of Knowledge Generation. The data show that the indicators are always practiced in the organization, with a 4.62 composite mean. No indicator posted a weighted mean lower than 4.50. Knowledge Generation as a KM process is prevalent within the university system. Shahzad et al. (2016) discovered that generating new knowledge affects organizational performance, including guaranteed success, market share, expansion, profitability, and inventiveness. Organizations should support research activities and promote collaborations and cooperation to foster knowledge development, as Igbinovia et al. (2017) suggested in their study on KM processes and systems.

The university has mechanisms for acquiring research knowledge from different sources such as academics, CHED, industries, and competitors, garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.65, which implies that this activity is always practiced within the university system. In an interview with the research director of one of the campuses, the interviewee stated that specific processes are being performed for the university to gather research knowledge from various sources, specifically from the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and industry partners. This knowledge is then utilized for research production planning and institutional research agenda. Ferraris et al. (2017) highlighted the importance of utilizing outside knowledge sources to support corporate innovation. Any management innovation project's effectiveness depends on the availability of knowledge sources from various partners (Mol et al., 2014). In this regard, a higher educational institution should only operate with others in implementing knowledge management but rather attempt to utilize various knowledge sources. According to Kim et al. (2015), knowledge gained from suppliers, clients, competitors, and consultants is essential for organizational innovation and success.

Sharing an equal-weighted mean of 4.64 and ranked 2nd, the university actively supports cooperation with other Higher Education Institutions on joint projects, encourages the creation of its own Research and Development centers by its faculty and staff, and encourages and supports faculty and staff to pursue graduate studies. Various interviews with the department concerned about these practices were conducted to validate these results, and regarding cooperation with other HEIs, the Linkages and International Affairs office of one of the campuses shared some information on collaboration with other local and foreign universities for research, delivery of instruction, training, academic exchange, and internationalization activities. These collaborations were forged to acquire and share the institutions' knowledge and best practices and improve the efficiency of delivering education while providing international exposure to multiple stakeholders. Collaboration is one of the significant requirements for government recognition. The policies and guidelines on foreign links and twinning projects were created by the CHED Memorandum Order 01 Series of 2000. By fostering cultural interchange in a global community, these policies and guidelines hope to increase the ties between Philippine and international institutions of higher learning in education, culture, society, economy, and politics (Narbarte, 2018). With this, one of the campuses has international linkages and joint projects with HEIs in countries like Canada, Spain, Thailand, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, China, Vietnam, Norway, Singapore, India, and South Korea.

According to Bozeman et al. (2013), the originality of innovations and their contribution to the perceived economic performance of the innovating firm, such as maintaining their competitive position, maintaining their profit margins, increase in their share of the international market, and their increase in profitability, are both positively impacted by collaborations with universities. In recent years, joint research initiatives, educational initiatives, exchange programs, and even rivalry have increased globally. Through increased numbers of international co-publications, cross-border patents, and human capital mobility, universities' third mission of commercialization and technology transfer—

which they pursue—encourages innovation engagements that go beyond the organizational and national level and increasingly take on a global character (Moortel et al., 2018).

As a university, it is mandated to perform the tri-fold functions expected from HEIs: instruction, extension, and research. Based on observation, all university system campuses have research centers that handle research-related initiatives and programs of the institutions. These centers are also responsible for the capacity building, research production, and publication of the faculties and staff. Higher education's traditional three primary purposes are research, instruction, and extension. For higher education to be a potent provider of valuable services and products to society, all four tasks are allegedly bound together, each in the service of the other (Tumapon, 2016). The university's research activities improve faculty research culture and quality and complement the National Higher Education Research Agenda (NHERA-2) Guidelines and Provisions of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) (Narbarte, 2018).

As part of the HRM practices, the HR Deputy Director confirmed that part of the benefits of the regular employees of the organization is the study grant for post-graduate degrees. Employees are given grants to enroll in graduate school programs offered by the institution and even by other institutions. This encourages faculty members to increase their knowledge and grow professionally. To date, thirty-three (33) faculty members and staff of one of the campuses are receiving the study grant for post-graduate studies. The result was also affirmed by the study conducted by Al Shobaki et al. (2017), wherein faculty members at Palestinian universities overwhelmingly approved of continuing education. An employee's motivation to share knowledge is influenced by the possibility of educational development as a non-financial reward (Mueller, 2012). According to research on the relationship between rewards, incentives, and knowledge management, rewards have a significant impact on how well people perform as they work to meet corporate goals. Positive relationships exist between incentives and KM (Wang et al., 2019).

Other indicators also posted high assessments from the faculty members. The university has mechanisms for creating research knowledge from different sources such as academics, CHED, industries, and competitors; and conducts benchmarking activities in the best Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in its field, ranked 5th with a weighted mean of 4.63; has strong linkages/partnership with companies and other organizations on joint Research and Development projects; and encourages student involvement in its research activities ranked 7th with a weighted mean of 4.62.

The university has well-established research programs and activities and posted the second-lowest rating among the indicators, with a weighted mean of 4.61. This item ranked ^{ninth} however is still verbally interpreted as always being practiced in the university system. This means there are existing research programs and activities within the university system. However, it needs more effective implementation. As affirmed by the Research Director of one of the campuses, a well-established institutional research agenda (IRA) is produced from the colleges' discipline-based research agenda. The topics presented in this agenda are anchored to the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations and the AmBisyon Natin 2040 of the Philippine government. The department concerned also stated that regular research training, fora, colloquiums, presentations, and retooling activities are being conducted to strengthen the research culture within the organization. Cascading of the IRA is being done to all faculty members during the start of the academic year through calls for papers and faculty meetings. Moreover, as discussed by the director, implementing more exciting and competitive rewards and incentives for research production will motivate the faculty and staff to conduct research. This was also affirmed by the study conducted by Dei et al. (2020), wherein universities have a strong community of practice (CoP), including informal and formal forums and meetings for advancing and preserving knowledge.

The university invites world-known educators to give lectures, which got the lowest rank among the indicators yet with a high weighted mean of 4.51, verbally interpreted as always being practiced in the university system. This means the university system has invited international guest lecturers to lecture on various topics and fields, however, irregularly. This has been affirmed by the HR Deputy Director of one of the campuses that the university has yet to invite any world-known lecturers to give lectures to its faculty and staff. The study conducted by Krogstie et al. (2018) indicated that most professors value guest lecturers, and it is excellent to have one or more talks per semester. A successful genuine learning strategy in on-campus learning communities is facilitated by inviting guest lecturers (Costello, 2012). Therefore, it is crucial to frequently invite foreign lecturers to extend the perspectives and expertise of the organization's members.

Table 6. Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Generation

Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Generation	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. actively supports cooperation with other Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) on joint projects.	4.64	Always	2.5
2. conducts benchmarking activities in its field's best Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).	4.63	Always	5.5
3. has mechanisms for creating research knowledge from different sources such as academics, CHED, industries, and competitors.	4.63	Always	5.5
4. has strong linkages/partnerships with companies and other organizations on joint Research and Development projects.	4.62	Always	7.5
5. has mechanisms for acquiring research knowledge from different sources such as academics, CHED, industries, and competitors.	4.65	Always	1
6. has well-established research programs and activities.	4.61	Always	9
7. encourages student involvement in its research activities.	4.62	Always	7.5
8. encourages the creation of its own Research and Development centers by its faculty and staff.	4.64	Always	2.5
9. encourages and supports faculty and staff to pursue graduate studies.	4.64	Always	2.5
10. invites world-known educators to give lectures.	4.51	Always	10
Composite Mean	4.62	Always	

Table 7 presents the level of faculty members' assessment of the organization's application of the Knowledge Management process in terms of Knowledge Storage. The data show that the indicators are often practiced in the organization with a 4.45 composite mean. No indicator posted a weighted mean higher than 4.49. The result implies that the activities under this dimension are moderately implemented in the university system. The faculty members are aware that the activities are being done, but only sometimes.

The university utilizes databases, repositories, and information technology applications to store knowledge for easy access by all academics ranked 1st among the indicators posting a weighted mean of 4.49. This implies that systems and information communication technologies are present in the organization to safeguard the information and knowledge available internally and access and utilize this information and knowledge for decision-making and delivery of processes. As affirmed by the MIS director of one of the campuses, databases, repositories, and ICT applications are utilized to aid information and knowledge sharing. The result was also affirmed by Yang et al. (2012) in the study on the relationship between IT applications and KM implementation that IT tools and applications significantly positively impact knowledge management. Owning a knowledge repository that can be

consulted when necessary is the essence of knowledge identification. A university should maintain a library of research interests, faculty research outputs, curriculum modification initiatives, student evaluation methods, and accountability data, among other things, as emphasized by Ojo (2016). In conclusion, a university needs a systematic repository for every piece of knowledge deemed essential to its operation. If considered appropriate, this repository could take the shape of business portals open to internal and external stakeholders.

The university stores knowledge (has an archive) on the content and implementation of the educational process; and utilizes various written devices such as newsletters and manuals to store knowledge captured from academics, getting the second highest weighted mean of 4.48. The result implies that these activities are being done within the university system to ensure that information and knowledge are easy to access and utilize for educational purposes. As validated by the key officers of one of the campuses, digital and hard copies of archives of knowledge are available at the libraries, resource centers, HR offices, and research centers. This stored knowledge is accessible to those who need it. The result was also affirmed by Superman (2018) in the study on KM practice among teachers, wherein storing knowledge in archives was the second most practiced activity in terms of Knowledge storage, and Oliva (2019), wherein tools for project management and knowledge storage had an average assessment of importance among the respondents. The requirement to save data in a readily accessible manner for future usage is constantly growing as data volume increases. A central archive with all data and information in a retrievable way is necessary for any work group, as Wright et al. (2018) also confirmed.

Other indicators under the Knowledge Storage process also got a moderate level of assessment, implying that they are being practiced often in the university system. The university has specialized software tools to organize repositories effectively and effectively, ranked 4th and posted a weighted mean of 4.46; stores knowledge (has an archive) on the content and implementation of research projects, ranked 5th with a weighted mean of 4.45. The university includes archiving the most important lectures and research among its best practices; has well-structured documentation of employees' competencies and achievements; and has different publications to display captured knowledge, all ranked 7th and got an equal-weighted mean of 4.44.

The university has a mechanism to patent and copyright new knowledge, ranked 9th with the lowest rating of 4.39. This means there are no or limited internal processes to patent and register the knowledge available in the university system for copyright. This was affirmed by the Research Director of one of the campuses that no office oversees the registration of Intellectual Properties of the institution, and the management has already opened discussions on this matter. According to the interviewee, the establishment of an IP office entails a significant requirement and strong commitment from the management as this will consume a lot of time and resources. Intellectual property rights are crucial for the advancement of social development in a knowledge-based economy (Lajpura et al., 2015). The expansion of a business can be protected by legally registering copyright, patents, and trademarks (Poncelaw.com, 2020). Without knowledge protection, businesses have little motivation to invest in employee training and create firm-specific knowledge since they anticipate that confidential information will be easily leaked to rival businesses through employee job hopping. As it limits knowledge sharing by assigning intellectual property rights (such as copyright, patent, and industrial design rights) only to the knowledge generator, knowledge protection encourages innovation (Qui et al., 2017).

After the end of its most significant projects, the university interviewed researchers to share and transfer knowledge based on experiences and posted the lowest weighted mean of 4.38. The result means that this indicator is often practiced at the university system, and little to no activity pertaining to an interview with the researchers is being conducted at the university system. Such an interview exists for employees leaving the company rather than for knowledge workers. As affirmed by the Research Director of one of the campuses, no explicit process addresses this practice for storing knowledge. The responsibility of a researcher ends after sending the manuscript of the study to the research center and having it published and presented. Key learnings from projects can assist teams in resolving current operational difficulties and enhancing performance indicators, according to the technical notes of the Inter-American Development Bank on Knowledge Capture through Interview (2012). A critical mass of pertinent knowledge that can be effectively shared through an integrated online knowledge base and used to develop or update training or other capacity-building efforts can be validated by the cumulative capture of critical learnings from multiple projects in each country (sub-)sector or business process.

Table 7. Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Storage

Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Storage	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. stores knowledge (has an archive) on the content and implementation of the educational process.	4.48	Often	2.5
2. includes archiving the most important lectures and research among its best practices.	4.44	Often	7
3. utilizes various written devices such as newsletters and manuals to store knowledge captured from academics.	4.48	Often	2.5
4. stores knowledge (has an archive) on the content and implementation of research projects.	4.45	Often	5
5. has a well-structured documentation of employees' competencies and achievements.	4.44	Often	7
6. interviews researchers after the end of its most significant projects to share and transfer knowledge based on experiences.	4.38	Often	10
7. has different publications to display captured knowledge.	4.44	Often	7
8. has a mechanism to patent and copyright new knowledge.	4.39	Often	9
9. has specialized software tools to organize repositories in a practical and usable manner.	4.46	Often	4
10. utilizes databases, repositories, and information technology applications to store knowledge for easy access by all academics.	4.49	Often	1
Composite Mean	4.45	Often	

Table 8 presents the data on faculty members' assessment of the KM Process in terms of Knowledge Sharing with a composite mean of 4.53 verbally interpreted as always being practiced in the university system. Six (6) indicators got a rating above 4.50, while others got below 4.49. The results indicate that the activities are being practiced in the university system. However, consistency in the implementation happens as reflected in the assessment levels. The result is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Weda (2018), wherein the knowledge-sharing process is always performed in EFL classrooms at Higher Education in Indonesia; however, it is inconsistent with the study conducted by Mulu et al. (2015) on knowledge sharing behavior of a university in Ethiopia wherein the result showed a low level of knowledge sharing practices implementation.

The university has libraries and resource centers to display and disseminate knowledge, posting the highest weighted mean of 4.64. This means that these facilities are available and accessible to all the faculty members whenever they need knowledge for personal and professional use. Based on observation, huge libraries and resource centers with modern and up-to-date software and applications are available on all campuses. These facilities are enough to cater to the academic-related needs of the

faculty members and especially its students. According to White (2012), libraries are essential to civilization because they are entryways to knowledge and culture. They provide resources and services that foster learning opportunities, encourage literacy and education, and aid in developing fresh viewpoints and ideas essential to developing an inventive and creative society. They also aid in preserving an accurate record of the information developed and gathered by earlier generations. Gadade (2021) confirmed that libraries' primary function and goals in knowledge management are to foster knowledge innovation. As bases for the collecting, processing, storage, and distribution of knowledge, libraries represent an essential link in the chain of scientific systems. In addition, libraries directly participate in scientific research, which is at the heart of the knowledge economic society. Libraries use technology and generate knowledge resources to research for simple information access.

The university has regular symposia, lectures, conferences, and teaching and training sessions to share knowledge, ranked as the ^{second} highest indicator with a weighted mean of 4.58. This means that the faculty members are aware of and experience various regular knowledge-sharing programs and activities. The result was affirmed by the Research Director and HR Deputy Director of one of the campuses. The interviewees mentioned that these programs and activities are part of the mandate and targets of their respective offices, which needs to be done regularly and should involve all employees. The Research Center is organizing research conferences, symposia, fora, retooling, and research training, while the HR Department is initiating faculty training, mentoring, webinars, and seminars. As recommended by Tan (2016) in her study, in order to debate ideas, concepts, and knowledge, universities may offer a variety of open and regular contact events like conferences, seminars, workshops, and KS sessions. These possibilities will help members understand the benefits of sharing their information, further increasing their propensity to interact with one another.

The university actively supports participation in multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and discipline-based research projects, posting the 3rd highest weighted mean of 4.55. The result directly affirms the second highest indicator under this dimension, which implies that the university system has programs for research projects, which are actively participated in by the faculty members. The authors are presenting research outputs from various disciplines and categories at various research conferences and fora. The Research Director affirms that research production in the organization is classified into three areas such as institutional, multidisciplinary, and discipline-based. These categories are anchored to the Institutional Research Agenda, and colleges provide targets for research production based on the agenda. Corresponding research grants are being provided. Much research is being produced under institutional and discipline-based agenda. However, the university needs a higher level of productivity for multidisciplinary research. The result also affirmed the result of the study conducted by Galgotia et al. (2022), wherein the authors concluded that one of the majorly deprived areas of education and research is multidisciplinary. Most studies show that expert research is more relaxed in higher education. Universities must encourage teachers and students to perform this kind of research because even most of the central archives and indexing services are founded on specialized research that needs more transdisciplinary and interdisciplinary research.

Other indicators under the Knowledge Sharing process also posted high-level and moderate-level assessments from the faculty members. The university sends out timely reports with appropriate information to academics, stakeholders, and relevant organizations; and has knowledge management practices that are communicated, making it easy to transfer best practices. Ranked 4th and garnered an equal-weighted mean of 4.53; our university has formalized the practice of transferring best practices such as documentation and lesson learned, ranked sixth and got a weighted mean of 4.51; identifies the root causes and solutions to frequently encountered problems; and knows the form that is readily accessible to educators who need it thru intranets and web-based platforms and software ranked 7th and got an equal-weighted mean of 4.49.

The university enables young academicians to become aware of different research topics, ranked ninth, and posted a moderate level of assessment from the faculty members with a weighted mean of 4.47. Despite the availability of institutional research agenda and different research categories, awareness among young faculty members could be higher. This means there needs to be a higher level of communication process to cascade the contents of the research agenda to all members of the teaching force. The Research Director affirmed that there are methods in place to build awareness among all employees of the university's research agenda. However, these need more effective implementation. According to Khan et al. (2018), university professors have already felt pressured to publish their papers and conduct research to keep up with the rapidly changing world and promote their careers. In order to allow university lecturers to engage in research activities in fields of interest, the author also suggested that colleges should offer possibilities for research in several fields within each discipline. For the advantage of research professors, competitive research projects aligned with their

personal and professional growth should be announced regularly under the direction of the higher education commission.

The university has an efficient system of coaching and mentoring young academicians, ranked tenth among the indicators with a weighted mean of 4.46. This implies an existing coaching and mentoring practice in the university system but is practiced and implemented often. As validated by the HR Deputy Director and the Research Director, a buddy system among the faculty members is being implemented in research production wherein a seasoned faculty member is partnered with a new faculty member for research production. The individual being mentored, more so than anybody else, can benefit from the growth and professional development that mentoring relationships can have on all parties involved. Exposure to a support system offers a learning opportunity that can assist the mentee in resolving challenging social and professional conundrums. For people to develop the skills necessary to stay relevant and competitive in the academic environment of higher education, mentoring and coaching help people build professional relationships (Carmel et al., 2015). Coaching and mentoring are ways to manage performance, promote change initiatives, and define the organization's culture (Conference Board, 2013).

Table 8. Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Sharing

Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Sharing	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. knows a form readily accessible to educators who need it thru intranets and web-based platforms and software.	4.49	Often	7.5
2. has libraries and resource centers to display and disseminate knowledge.	4.64	Always	1
3. Send timely reports to academics, stakeholders, and relevant organizations with appropriate information.	4.53	Always	4.5
4. has regular symposia, lectures, conferences, and teaching and training sessions to share knowledge.	4.58	Always	2
5. has an efficient system of coaching and mentoring young academicians.	4.46	Often	10
6. enables young academicians to become aware of different research topics.	4.47	Often	9
7. actively supports participation in multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and discipline-based research projects.	4.55	Always	3
8. has formalized transferring best practices such as documentation and lesson learned.	4.51	Always	6
9. identifies the root causes and solutions to frequently encountered problems.	4.49	Often	7.5
10. has knowledge management practices that are communicated, making it easy to transfer best practices.	4.53	Always	4.5
Composite Mean	4.53	Always	

Table 9 presents the data on the level of faculty members' assessment of the KM Process in terms of Knowledge Application with a composite mean of 4.49 verbally interpreted as being practiced often in the university system. Seven (7) indicators got a rating above 4.50, while others got below 4.49. The results indicate that the activities are being practiced in the organization; however, just like with the activities under Knowledge storage, inconsistencies in the implementation happen, as reflected in the level of assessments made by the faculty members. This is inconsistent with the study conducted by Fiscal (2019) and Fiscal (2021), wherein knowledge application activities have long been done in state colleges in the Philippines. The findings of a study by Al-Tahaina et al. (2015) that sought to estimate the degree of knowledge application in physical education colleges in Jordanian universities contradict this as well, as they showed that the degree of knowledge application implementation process had been generally high.

The university utilizes knowledge embedded in procedures, rules, norms, and processes that guide future behavior and got the highest weighted mean of 4.55 among all indicators. This implies that explicit knowledge is widely available and accessible for all the faculty members in the university system to guide them in the performance of process and decision-making activities. As an ISO-certified university, it is imperative to explicitly present information and knowledge on how work processes and procedures should be done using manuals. These manuals facilitate easy sharing and application of knowledge among all the organization's members. Other organization members can internalize the explicit knowledge in such papers to enlarge their tacit knowledge base by reading documents or manuals regarding their work and the organization and commenting on them (Nonaka et al., 2015). Because of knowledge management and efficient documentation procedures, staff members do not need to learn new tasks independently. Instead, they can get assistance from former workers. This helps organizations become more productive while reducing risks and losses to the company if staff members decide to retire or leave (valamis.com, 2022).

The university applies best practices in the educational process, posting the second-highest weighted mean of 4.53, which signifies that the indicator is always applied in the context of the university system. This implies that the university system conducts benchmarking activities with various reputable universities and industry partners on their best practices and applies them to the educational processes of the university system. This has been affirmed in an interview with the Assistant Vice President for Academics and Research of one of the campuses where local and international benchmarking visits were done. It will be done to check the KM best practices other universities are doing and apply them to the university. Pre-pandemic, the university benchmarked reputable foreign universities in Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand, South Korea, Hongkong, China, Japan, Taiwan, Indonesia, and the USA. Locally, the university officials were able to benchmark the University of Sto. Tomas, University of the Philippines, De La Salle University, Ateneo De Manila University, University of San Carlos, University of the Visayas, University of Cordilleras, and University of Cebu. Applying effective KM best practices can assist academia in realizing its objectives of safeguarding resources, comprehending the knowledge it possesses, disseminating that knowledge among its community, and understanding its internal processes to enhance the institution's administrative and scholarly activities, with a focus on knowledge production and increased discovery, creating curriculum aids, creating knowledge repositories, and turning information into knowledge to enhance learning (Khakpour, 2015).

The university applies knowledge to critical competitive needs and quickly links sources of knowledge in problem-solving was the 3rd highest rated indicator with a weighted mean of 4.51. This implies that the university system's available data, information, and knowledge are always utilized to aid problem-solving and decision-making. Making data-based decisions is crucial for improving schools (Schildkamp et al., 2019). Better data presents chances to make better business decisions, particularly in academic settings, according to Bynnjolfsson et al. (2016). According to research, data-based decision-making may also improve instructors' instructional skills and student learning and accomplishment (Lai et al., 2014; McNaughton et al., 2012; Poortman et al., 2016; Van Geel et al., 2016).

Three indicators shared the same weighted mean of 4.50, and all ranked 5th. These are the university applying historical data and information to solve new challenges, having methods to research and critically evaluate knowledge to generate new patterns and knowledge for further use, and applying new technology and specific scientific method or transient procedure to develop new research projects. The university applies best practices in research projects; and applies best practices in research projects, ranked 7th and posted an equal-weighted mean of 4.49.

The university has different methods for faculty and staff to further develop and apply their knowledge to new situations, ranked 9th among all the indicators, and posted a weighted mean of 4.46. This means that the activity is often practiced within the university system. This also implies that the

faculty members need to be exposed to various available methods and techniques to solve work-related and new situations using the knowledge available in the university system. This indicator can be categorized as a motivational factor to share knowledge. Employee empowerment is viewed as a motivational strategy to improve performance by giving employees more opportunities to participate in and influence decisions. It focuses primarily on fostering motivation, building trust, allowing employees to participate in decision-making, and reducing any barriers between them and upper management (Meyerson et al., 2012). Employee empowerment significantly influences organizational effectiveness (Gholami et al., 2013; Insan et al., 2013).

The university used disposable intellectual potential and posted the lowest weighted mean of 4.44. This means that the item is the least practiced activity in the university system among all indicators. Intellectual Capital (IC) is comprised of every employee contributing valuable knowledge, skills, and experience to their organization. The result implies that the individual-contributed knowledge of the employees is rarely applied in the problem-solving and decision-making processes of the university system. Knowledge-based HRM techniques play a role in promoting and utilizing IC in an organization's success and innovation. According to Kianto et al. (2017), knowledge-based HRM practices impact the three primary categories of IC—human, structural, and relational capital—which affect innovation performance. Additionally, according to Gogan et al. (2016), the usage of intellectual capital directly correlates with and influences organizational success.

Table 9. Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Application

Knowledge Management Process in Terms of Knowledge Application	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. has different methods for faculty and staff to further develop and apply their knowledge to new situations.	4.46	Often	9
2. applies best practices in the educational process.	4.53	Always	2
3. utilizes knowledge embedded in procedures, rules, norms, and processes that guide future behavior.	4.55	Always	1
4. applies knowledge to critical competitive needs and quickly links sources of knowledge in problem-solving.	4.51	Always	3
5. applies historical data and information in solving new challenges.	4.50	Always	5
6. makes use of disposable intellectual potential.	4.44	Often	10
7. has methods to research and critically evaluate knowledge to generate new patterns and knowledge for further use.	4.50	Always	5
8. applies best practices in research projects.	4.49	Often	7.5
9. applies new technology and specific scientific methods or transient procedures to develop research projects.	4.50	Always	5
10. applies new technology and specific scientific method or transient procedure for marketing its research and educational potential.	4.49	Often	7.5
Composite Mean	4.49	Often	

Table 10 summarizes the composite mean scores of the faculty member's assessments on implementing the Knowledge Management Process in the university system, with a grand composite mean of 4.52. Like the Key Factors of KM Practices, the KM Process is always practiced in the university system. A similar result has been affirmed by the study conducted by Fiscal (2019), wherein the participants responded that the KM Process is always practiced in state universities in the Philippines. Individual mean scores of each dimension correspond to the result of the study conducted by Raudeliuniene et al. (2020) on KM Practice in General Education schools, wherein the authors noted that all KM process is being practiced. However, problems with implementing some activities under each process exist, affecting the entire KM process cycle.

It can be seen from the table that only Knowledge Generation and Knowledge Sharing got an "always" verbal interpretation. Knowledge Generation got the highest composite mean of 4.62, followed by Knowledge Sharing with a 4.53 composite mean. The results imply that these two dimensions are always practiced within the university system. At the same time, Knowledge Application (4.49) and Knowledge Storage (4.45) are being practiced "often" on all campuses. It means that some indicators need enhancement in terms of implementation. This contradicts the study conducted by Superman et al. (2018) on KM practices among teachers, wherein among all the dimensions of the KM Process, the respondents practice a high level of Knowledge storage. However, knowledge application got a moderate level of practice among the respondents.

In the study conducted by Shahzad et al. (2016), the researchers discovered that the Knowledge Generation stage impacts organizational performance, which is defined in a model that includes successfulness, market share, growth, profitability, and innovativeness. To promote organizational success, organizations must ensure that all KM techniques are correctly applied. In their study, Palacios et al. (2013) observed that businesses need to strengthen information sharing because doing so will favor the development of superior company performance.

Table 10. Summary Table on Knowledge Management Process

Knowledge Management Process	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Knowledge Generation	4.62	Always	1
2. Knowledge Storage	4.45	Often	4
3. Knowledge Sharing	4.53	Always	2
4. Knowledge Application	4.49	Often	3
Grand Composite Mean	4.52	Always	

Table 11 presents the level of faculty members' assessment of the KM Performance Outcomes in teaching. The results show that KM implementation in the university system has a moderate impact on teaching, with a composite mean of 4.49 verbally interpreted as often observed and experienced by the faculty members, which is consistent with the inconsistencies in the faculty member's assessment of KM practices and process in the university system. Seven (7) indicators posted a high rating from the faculty members, while only three (3) got a moderate rating. Teaching as the core component of the existence of an academic institution should take the highest level of impact for Knowledge Management implementation, but this result presented otherwise. This means a gap exists in how the management implements KM in the university system. The result contradicts the study conducted by Fiscal (2019), wherein KM implementation in state universities in the Philippines has an excellent impact on the quality of teaching. This was also affirmed by the study conducted by Goncalves Costa et al. (2021) on Knowledge Management in Brazilian schools, wherein the authors concluded that Knowledge Management enhances the quality of instruction throughout the school by facilitating the effective exchange of knowledge through organizational procedures and processes.

The university has improved the relevance of courses to industry practices and standards, ranked 1st, and posted the highest rating from the faculty members with a weighted mean of 4.61. This implies that knowledge from external sources like industries is being utilized and incorporated into the curriculum of the university system's programs. This is evident in the vision of one of the campuses wherein the inclusion of being an industry-driven university statement in its vision was made. The AVP for Academics and Research of one of the campuses affirmed that as part of the curriculum review of all the programs, all stakeholders, especially industry experts, are invited to align the curricula to industry practices and standards. Moreover, each college or program has a board of industry advisors who assists and guides in crafting, aligning, and improving curriculum content based

on industry standards and requirements. According to a policy established by the Philippine Commission on Higher Education (CHED), all HEIs must implement outcomes-based education (OBE). OBE is a government-mandated educational reform that aims to improve quality and sustainability. It requires critical education stakeholders, including industry partners, to collaborate continuously to align teaching, learning, assessment, outcomes, and quality improvement with market norms and practices. Galeon et al.'s study (2020) discovered an urgent need to create a knowledge network to encourage stakeholder engagement and create an institutional memory to promote OBE implementation. A system combining OBE and KM must be created to ensure that the quality of instruction delivered in HEIs continues to improve.

The university has better and more modern teaching methodologies and more effective teaching and learning processes; both ranked second and obtained a weighted mean of 4.54. The result implies that the university system always uses various modern and relevant teaching styles and methods to facilitate learning. The advanced technological innovations and demands of learners drive this. Based on observation, one of the campuses currently offers its programs in hybrid mode – a combination of in-person classes and online learning. Also, some courses are being delivered in the Hy Flex method wherein students can attend the real-time class in person or online. These methodologies require advanced technological infrastructure to facilitate.

Moreover, each classroom, laboratory, and simulator is equipped with modern equipment for teachers and students to use during in-person classes. Indeed, technology is changing the classroom experience. As noted by Namitha (2018) in her study, universities must have interactive teaching, and the arrival of multimedia technology and the emergence of a digitally sophisticated student population will inevitably change the function of education. Current tools and equipment use boosts students' learning and involvement, according to the most recent research on how exactly modern students choose to use technology today and how it affects their learning. When technology is used to help, they find it to be much more interactive and fuller of intriguing places. Knowledge transfer has become incredibly simple, practical, and efficient (Raja et al., 2018). Digital cameras, projectors, mind-training software, laptops, PowerPoint presentations, and 3D visualization tools are just a few examples of the technological advancements that have made it easier for teachers to assist pupils in understanding concepts (Nagasubramani et al., 2018).

The university has improved student projects and output and has improved the quality of learning assessment and evaluation tools, ranked 4th, and posted an equal-weighted mean of 4.53. The university has improved the performance ratings of the faculty members, and has improved learning and adapting capability, ranked 6th, and garnered a weighted mean of 4.51. The organization has allocated more funds to develop facilities and infrastructure facilitating knowledge management, ranked 8th, and posted a weighted mean of 4.44.

The university has increased the doctorate to bachelor's degree holder ratio for the faculty members, ranked 9th among the indicators with a weighted mean of 4.35. This implies that an observable low number of faculty members possess a post-graduate degree. This contradicts the data provided by the HR Department of one of the campuses wherein 70% of its faculty members for all programs have post-graduate degrees, and 33 are currently enrolled in their respective programs. The office also discussed that faculty members are encouraged to obtain post-graduate degrees as this is a criterion for programs and institutional accreditation. Garba et al. (2021), in their study on the academic staff deficit in Nigeria's higher education institutions, emphasized the detrimental effects of academic staff credentials that fell short of the criteria for knowledge transmission. This involves low output, subpar instruction, overcrowding, and subpar education. The authors suggested that HEIs construct additional post-graduate education programs, expand in-service and staff development programs, and plan strategically for their human resources. Poor capacity development for lecturers causes specific programs to lose their accreditation or causes it to fluctuate (Ukaegbu et al., 2017).

The university has developed a better faculty-to-student ratio and garnered the lowest weighted mean of 4.30. The result implies that the number of students per class is more than the maximum required and the ideal ratio for learning. The data provided by the Registrar's Office of one of the campuses that oversee room allocation and student enrollment shows that specific courses and programs go beyond the required faculty-to-student ratio. The average class size for lecture classes is 50 students, while 25 students for laboratory (specialized) classes and 50 for computer laboratory classes. The office also discussed that this is sometimes due to inadequate faculty members and insufficient classrooms and laboratories. Class size is typically correlated with the number of pupils per teacher, and it is generally accepted that smaller classrooms offer better teaching and learning. Many nations, including the USA, Europe, China, Japan, and many others, share this opinion and have implemented laws to reduce class sizes (Blatchford et al., 2012). According to Yelkpiieri et al. (2012), big class sizes make it difficult for weaker students to learn and transfer knowledge. This suggests that

pupils who might require it need to receive individualized care. Regardless of the educational setting or level, more is needed to support high-quality teaching and learning. Ayeni et al. (2016) also found that teaching business education effectively in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State, Nigeria, is negatively impacted by large class sizes. According to the study, it results in poor classroom management, inefficient student control, poor planning and evaluation, and increased teacher workload.

Table 11. Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes in Terms of Teaching

Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes in Terms of Teaching	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. has developed a better faculty-to-student ratio.	4.30	Often	10
2. has increased the doctorate to bachelor's degree holder ratio for faculty members.	4.35	Often	9
3. has improved learning and adapting capability.	4.51	Always	6.5
4. has improved the relevance of courses to industry practices and standards.	4.61	Always	1
5. has better and more modern teaching methodologies.	4.54	Always	2.5
6. has a more effective teaching and learning process.	4.54	Always	2.5
7. has improved student projects and outputs.	4.53	Always	4.5
8. has improved the quality of learning assessment and evaluation tools.	4.53	Always	4.5
9. has improved the performance ratings of the faculty members.	4.51	Always	6.5
10. has allocated more funds to develop facilities and infrastructure facilitating knowledge management.	4.44	Often	8
Composite Mean	4.49	Often	

Table 12 presents the respondent's assessment of Knowledge Management Practices and KM Process to Research performance outcomes. The data shows a composite mean of 4.47 verbally interpreted as often. This means that implementing KM Practices and KM processes moderately impacts the outcome level of the university system's research area. Only one (1) indicator got a high rating, while the rest posted moderate ratings, at most 4.49. This contradicts the study conducted by Fiscal (2019) and Fiscal (2021) on the impact of KM implementation in the Research area, wherein the respondents from various state universities rated the impact very good. Organizational performance can benefit significantly from knowledge-sharing techniques (Onyancha, 2016; Miloff et al., 2013). Some of these include more cross-border collaboration in research, transparency in research enabling greater data reuse, and international support for university research.

The university has improved the innovation and creativity of the faculty and staff through KM implementation, ranked 1st, and garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.51 verbally interpreted as often observed as the impact of Knowledge Management implementation at the university system. This implies that KM implementation impacts the faculty members' creativity and innovativeness in sharing their knowledge. There is empirical data about how knowledge production, integration, and application

affect the innovation and performance of academic staff and the organization (Akhavan et al., 2016; Ferraris et al., 2017; Cheng et al., 2019; Haimanot et al., 2019; Tamara, 2018; Akram et al., 2018; Thi Phuong et al., 2019; Afsar et al., 2019; Cheng et al. One is the study by Mardani et al. (2018) that identified KM as a critical mechanism for improving performance and creativity. According to research, KM enhances employees' capacity for innovation (Siddiqui et al., 2019). Individual and team creativity development depends heavily on knowledge management (Ali et al., 2019; Men et al., 2019).

The university has increased its research productivity/research publication in the academic journals indexed by ISI, Scopus, and other indexing bodies databases posted the second highest weighted mean of 4.48 but verbally interpreted as often observed as the impact of Knowledge Management implementation at the university system. This implies that the university system is conducting the publication of research to various indexing body databases such as ISI and Scopus. As validated by the Research office of one of the campuses, the university targets to publish much research in Scopus in the next 2.5 years, as the following QS ranking will be done in 2025. QS only looks at a university's research performance with QS stars in the quality of publication in Scopus. From 2016 to 2021, the university was able to publish only thirty research outputs in Scopus. This low publication data to Scopus-indexed journals parallels Rogayan Jr. (2022) and Anito et al. (2020), which revealed that their HEI-respondents also registered very few papers published from 2016-2020 and 2008-2017, respectively. In order to boost the credibility of their work and that of the researcher, researchers should make an effort to submit and publish their outputs to journals (Brown, 2017). This will also ensure the information is preserved in a permanent, searchable record. Based on the April 2020 Scopus data, the Philippines was rated sixth among the ten (10) member states of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) area by Scimago Institutions Ranking (2020). There are 38,024 documents from the nation in the Scopus database, 34,839 of which can be cited. The nation reported 571,112 total citations, including 55,765 self-citations, and it is safe to assume that this number comprises the research outputs created and disseminated by academic scholars at the university system.

The university has increased its research production among faculty and students, posting the 3rd highest weighted mean of 4.48 but verbally interpreted as often observed as the impact of Knowledge Management implementation at the university system. This is consistent with the discussion of the results on the increased research publication and database indexing. The result implies that research is given importance by both the employees and the students at the university system. Based on observation, research is embedded, integrated, and incorporated into the curriculum of all the programs, from High School to Post-Graduate Degree programs, which is required for graduation. This is also a part of employee performance evaluation, especially for faculty members. Thus, resulting in a higher number of research production. As verified by the HR and Research Office Directors, there is also a motivation and reward incentive provided to the faculty and staff who will engage in research production. The rewards and incentives differ based on the nature of the study the researchers will work on. The result is consistent with Basiru's (2018) study, which indicated a moderately low level of research productivity among academic staff of private universities in Southwest Nigeria. The result was unparalleled to Okenedo's (2015) findings on the research and publication productivity of academic staff and students in public universities in Southwest Nigeria, revealing high productivity within the period of 2009- 2014.

The university has enhanced its research motivation programs; has increased the facilitation of inter-disciplinary research; has provided easy access to research grants and facilities; has increased the number of local and international research presentations; and has increased the impact factor or frequency which the average article of the scholars in a journal has been cited in a particular year all ranked 5th and garnered the same weighted mean of 4.47.

The university has increased the h-index or productivity and citation impact of the publications of a researcher posted a weighted mean of 4.46 verbally interpreted as often observed as the impact of Knowledge Management implementation at the university system, and ranked 9th among all indicators. The result needs to be consistent with the assessment of the increase in research production among the faculty members and the increase in research publication in academic journals. This indicates that the quality of the research outputs and publications could be more worthy of citation and recognized and considered essential sources by other researchers. This is inconsistent with the study by Rogayan Jr. (2022) on the research productivity of a state university in Central Luzon, Philippines, wherein it revealed a high research citation of the papers published by the institution in international refereed journals. However, the result is parallel with the study of the research productivity of SUC Managers in Eastern Visayas, Philippines revealing a shallow citation impact on the research outputs of the respondents. According to the research director of one of the campuses, the university is not very particular anymore with this metric since QS needs to acknowledge this. Since

the university system is QS-g geared, resources are now being diverted to Scopus, which is the sole basis for research productivity for QS ranking.

The university has increased the number of global citations of the university's published research works, ranking 10th among all the indicators with a weighted mean of 4.45. This result implies a low level of global citation for the research published in reputable international and local research publications. This is inconsistent with the high level of faculty member's assessment of the increased research production among employees and students at the university system. The Research Office also affirmed that a low citation level had been recorded for the research publications. Peris-Ortiz et al. (2023) observed that although it is challenging to quantify exploration outputs of HEIs in the form of research directly, they can be measured through bibliometric indicators based on the papers published in scholarly publications. The effectiveness of knowledge creation and global leadership is linked to an institution's excellence in research production, demonstrated by the publication of research articles in high-impact journals and the volume of citations for articles that have already been published (Chang et al., 2016).

Table 12. Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes in Terms of Research

Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes in Terms of Research	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. has increased its research production among faculty and students.	4.48	Often	3
2. has improved the innovation and creativity of the faculty and staff.	4.51	Always	1
3. has increased its research productivity/research publication in the academic journals indexed by ISI, Scopus, and other indexing bodies databases.	4.49	Often	2
4. has increased the global citations of the university's published research works.	4.45	Often	10
5. has increased the h-index or productivity and citation impact of a researcher's publications.	4.46	Often	8.5
6. has increased the impact factor or frequency in which the average article of the scholars in a journal has been cited in a particular year.	4.46	Often	8.5
7. enhanced its research motivation programs.	4.47	Often	5.5
8. has increased the facilitation of interdisciplinary research.	4.47	Often	5.5
9. has provided easy access to research grants and facilities.	4.47	Often	5.5
10. has increased the number of local and international research presentations.	4.47	Often	5.5
Composite Mean	4.47	Often	

Table 13 presents the data on the level of faculty members' assessment of the performance outcomes of Knowledge Management Practices and KM Processes in terms of International Outlook with a composite mean of 4.31 verbally interpreted as often observed as the impact of Knowledge

Management implementation in the university system. Implementing KM Practices and processes moderately impacts the performance outcomes of the university system's internationalization activities and initiatives. All indicators posted a moderate rating, not higher than 4.49. This contradicts the study conducted by Fiscal (2019) on the impact of KM implementation on the international outlook, wherein the respondents from various state universities in the country rated the impact very good. This also is contrary to the findings of the study done by Kirugumi (2022), whose author concluded that knowledge management capabilities significantly and favorably influenced the level of internationalization. According to Houssaini (2019), internationalization incorporates a variety of knowledge factors, including knowledge of networks, internationalization knowledge, and technological knowledge. Additionally, firms must review their expertise and grow it when they transcend international boundaries. Research has shown that through enhancing resources, experience, and skills through various inter-institutional networks and partnerships, internationalization strengthens organizational studies and knowledge-generating capabilities (Knight et al., 2018).

The university has increased its number of industry partnerships for employment and training, ranked 1st, and garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.48. This means that the university system has numerous partner companies from various industries for the training of both the students and employees and the employment of its graduates. The result was affirmed by one of the campuses' Placement Offices and Internship Office. One of the campuses has partnered with twenty-four (24) local companies and four (4) international companies to employ its graduates. These companies are from various industries, such as hospitality, engineering, medicine, business process outsourcing, marketing, human resource, and maritime. The university has forged partnerships with 143 companies in various fields regarding internship training. These companies serve as internship and training centers for their students. According to Elezi (2021), creating partnerships gives HEI a chance to improve intellectual capacity accessibility, keep enhancing the value of their academic courses, and provide a more sustainable response to problems faced by the higher education industry. According to Junejo et al. (2018), higher education institutions now view industry-university links as crucial and relevant at both the institutional and national levels.

The university has increased its international collaborations and partnerships for education and research, posting the second-highest weighted mean of 4.47. This implies that apart from an increase in local and national partnerships for employment and training, there is also a moderate increase in international linkages and partnerships for education and research areas of the university system. These partnerships provide the employees and students with an avenue to collaborate and share knowledge with foreign universities. This is affirmed by the Linkages and International Affairs Office of one of the campuses. Currently, the campus has eighty-three (83) partner international organizations and foreign universities and fifty-nine (59) local partners for academic exchange programs and projects. These partnerships were forged to allow students and employees to share knowledge through attending short-term courses, cultural exchange programs, research presentations, staff mobility programs, academic competitions, and conferences. Partnerships with foreign universities allow both domestic and international students to travel abroad for various study-related programs (scholarshubafrika.com, 2019). Institutions can provide international experiences, such as study abroad programs and staff exchanges, in addition to research possibilities and cultural knowledge. Benefits for teaching include the creation of curricula and degrees in association with associate schools (QS.com, 2019).

The university has increased its outbound and inbound student mobility programs, posting the 3rd highest weighted mean of 4.44. The result implies that faculty members observed a moderate increase in the number of exchange students coming in and sent out to partner foreign universities. The establishment of the International Affairs Office on each of the campuses paved the way for the internationalization activities and initiatives of the university system. From the data provided by one of the units, 98 students were sent to various academic and cultural exchange programs in the last three (3) academic years, in-person and virtual, while 53 inbound students were accepted to participate in short-term programs, academic and cultural exchange programs, in-person or virtual. The initiatives correspond to the vision of the university system of becoming an industry-driven and internationally-known educational institution. The result is inconsistent with the study conducted by Khatun et al. (2022) on Knowledge Management practices of a premier school in India, revealing a relatively low and less result for the indicator.

All other indicators garnered a moderate rating from the faculty members. The university has improved its ranking and performance from the recognized international rankings and ratings, ranked 4th and posted a weighted mean of 4.41; has increased its outbound and inbound faculty and staff mobility programs, ranked 5th with 4.37 weighted mean; has more benchmarking visits from other international academic institutions ranked 6th with 4.28 weighted mean; has increased its international

to domestic student ratio ranked 7th with 4.21 weighted mean; has submitted itself to Knowledge Management audit and accreditation ranked 8th with 4.17 weighted mean.

The university has integrated provisions of Knowledge Management implementation into its internationalization activities and posted the second-lowest rating of 4.16. This implies that provisions of KM implementation as part of the Internationalization activities and programs of the university system are not present and are not included in the internationalization (IZN) plan and targets. The result needs to be consistent with the confirmation of the Linkages and International Affairs Supervisor of one of the campuses that there are provisions about KM on the IZN plans of the university. The provisions include the targets for inbound and outbound students, faculty, and staff for various exchange programs, organizing short-term programs, and international collaborations and partnerships. There could be confusion among the respondents about the interconnectedness of KM and internationalization initiatives of the university system since internationalization has been synonymous with international mobility. According to Gacel-Avila (2021), colleges must reconsider and restructure their internationalization initiatives after the pandemic. The internationalization of the curriculum (IoC) and initiatives for internationalization at home (IaH) should then be the main areas of concentration for HEIs. By internationalizing programs, curricula, and pedagogies for knowledge sharing, these initiatives could achieve comparable results among students without mobility.

The university has increased its international to domestic-faculty and staff ratio, ranked 10th, and posted the lowest weighted mean of 4.12. The result implies that the university system only employs foreign nationals as part of its workforce. As confirmed by the HR Deputy Director of one of the campuses, no foreign national is currently a part of its workforce, and has yet to make provisions on the HR plans to hire one. The international to domestic faculty and staff ratio is a part of the QS Stars ranking criteria. This indicator examines the proportion of foreign academic employees to all other employees. An institution will profit from the diversity and collaboration in research and teaching if it attracts many international faculty.

Table 13. Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes in Terms of International Outlook

Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes in Terms of International Outlook	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. has increased its international-to-domestic student ratio.	4.21	Often	7
2. has increased its international to domestic-faculty and staff ratio.	4.12	Often	10
3. has increased its international collaborations and partnerships for education and research.	4.47	Often	2
4. has increased its number of industry partnerships for employment and training.	4.48	Often	1
5. has increased its outbound and inbound student mobility programs.	4.44	Often	3
6. has increased its outbound and inbound faculty and staff mobility programs.	4.37	Often	5
7. has more benchmarking visits from other international academic institutions.	4.28	Often	6
8. has improved its ranking and performance from the recognized international rankings and ratings.	4.41	Often	4
9. has integrated provisions of Knowledge Management implementation into its internationalization activities.	4.16	Often	9
10. has submitted itself to Knowledge Management audit and accreditation.	4.17	Often	8
Composite Mean	4.31	Often	

Table 14 summarizes the average composite mean scores of the faculty member's assessments on the Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes level in the university system with a grand composite mean of 4.42. The mean scores for teaching (4.49), research (4.47), and international

outlook (4.31) indicate that the university system has a moderate level of performance outcomes, and these are often observed and felt by the respondents. This contradicts the result of the study conducted by Fiscal (2019) on Knowledge Management of State Universities in the Philippines, wherein excellent performance outcomes in state universities in the Philippines exist in all the above dimensions, and Fiscal (2021) on the impact of KM enablers on the performance outcomes of state universities in the Philippines wherein the study revealed that critical factors of knowledge management have an excellent impact to teaching, research, international outlook dimensions.

It was stated that knowledge management concepts and techniques could, in fact, help and could advance the cause of research in the university based on the case of the Singapore Management University (Ahmadi et al., 2012). Khakpour (2015) added that knowledge management activities' roles and influences on curriculum development, research, and educational planning always have favorable effects on the business. Du (2021) asserts that the employment of knowledge management activities, such as the production, synthesis, distribution, and dissemination of knowledge, aids universities in achieving their objectives of global management and performance enhancement. With knowledge management, universities create novel connections between employment and education, encourage the adoption of new information, learn from experience, and foster academic success.

Table 14. Summary Table on Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes

Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Teaching	4.49	Often	1
2. Research	4.47	Often	2
3. International Outlook	4.31	Often	3
Grand Composite Mean	4.42	Often	

Table 15 compares responses on knowledge management practices when grouped according to profile. It was revealed that there was a significant difference in employee motivation when grouped according to qualifications since the obtained p-value of 0.049 was less than the alpha level. This means that the responses differ, and based on the post hoc test, it was found that those with bachelor's degrees are more motivated than others. This is because young knowledge workers and faculty members need more experience and knowledge on how they will execute their roles and responsibilities, given the number of years they have been working; thus, they are more motivated to create, share, store, and apply knowledge.

All knowledge workers are valuable and ought to be shared and protected. According to Prelog et al. (2019), senior employees may be reluctant to impart their knowledge to younger employees out of concern that they would be replaced. Since they have less experience, younger employees need to learn new skills when they begin working at a new place of employment. They learn the most from senior staff members with experience and expertise. Fresh graduates and those with a bachelor's degree have less knowledge management experience and are more eager to share and take in information. Botjancic et al. (2019) found a statistically significant difference in the desire for knowledge sharing between the younger and middle-aged staff groups. According to the data, considerable statistical differences exist between the youngest group of employees and the other age groups, particularly regarding how willing they are to share their knowledge. Employees need more motivation to share their knowledge as they get older. According to L. Finkelstein and colleagues (2013), middle-aged workers may believe that younger workers are vying for their positions, which makes them defensive of their knowledge. Younger workers are more willing to share their knowledge since they need to learn a lot, and they anticipate that by doing so, other workers will do the same for them. According to the social exchange theory, interactions between coworkers are built on a shared expectation from both parties that reciprocity will be motivated by voluntary behaviors, which does, in fact, frequently happen (Blau, 1964). Senior employees are the least motivated of all age groups, which has implications for workplace organizations because this age group has the most tacit knowledge—knowledge that is challenging to transmit and record—compared to other age groups. The only way for firms to keep this expertise is to impart it to younger staff. Thus, it is crucial that senior staff feel inspired to do so.

This study also found significant differences in organizational culture and employee motivation when grouped according to area of specialization. The result shows that those in culinary, tourism, and hospitality management better assess the organization's culture and are more motivated because the result p-value of organizational culture and employee motivation were less than the alpha

level. Hospitality professionals understand the importance of utilizing up-to-date knowledge and information to serve their customers from varied lifestyles better. Thus, organizational culture and HRM practices that encourage knowledge management objectify their ultimate roles of satisfying customers through services based on up-to-date knowledge and information about their field.

A little research has been done to determine what inspires some hospitality industry workers, why they stay, and what else businesses can do to draw and keep these workers. According to Kim et al.'s (2013) study, hotel employees' knowledge-sharing and knowledge-accumulation activities are important drivers of their service innovation behavior. Interestingly, knowledge donation appears to have less impact on hotel staff members' innovative service conduct. An article published by Bloomfire (2021) claims that people working in the hospitality business are fully aware of the value of having access to comprehensive, specialized knowledge. They value this since the beautiful experiences they can give their clients drive them. Empirical evidence or literature does not support why those in the culinary, tourist, and hospitality industries have such high opinions of corporate culture. Organizational culture significantly impacts organizations' performance and long-term success in terms of values and practices (Lone, 2013; Fiscal, 2019; Lee et al., 2012; Goncalves-Costa et al., 2021).

Table 15. Difference of Responses on the Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices When Grouped According to Profile

Campus	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Organizational Culture	0.351	0.843	Not Significant
Information Technology	2.286	0.061	Not Significant
Employee Motivation	0.649	0.628	Not Significant
Age			
Organizational Culture	1.696	0.136	Not Significant
Information Technology	1.251	0.286	Not Significant
Employee Motivation	0.934	0.460	Not Significant
Gender			
Organizational Culture	0.744	0.389	Not Significant
Information Technology	0.008	0.930	Not Significant
Employee Motivation	2.102	0.148	Not Significant
Qualifications			
Organizational Culture	0.493	0.611	Not Significant
Information Technology	1.069	0.345	Not Significant
Employee Motivation	3.057	0.049	Significant
Area of Specialization			
Organizational Culture	2.293	0.028	Significant
Information Technology	0.368	0.920	Not Significant
Employee Motivation	3.040	0.004	Significant
Tenure Ship			
Organizational Culture	1.436	0.223	Not Significant
Information Technology	2.230	0.067	Not Significant
Employee Motivation	1.808	0.128	Not Significant

Table 16 compares responses on the Knowledge Management Process when grouped according to profile. Results revealed that there were significant differences in knowledge generation ($p = 0.037$), storage ($p = 0.011$), and sharing ($p = 0.044$) when grouped according to campus because the computed p-values were less than the alpha level. This only implies that the responses differ statistically, and based on the test conducted, LPU Laguna participants have a more positive assessment. This is because the campus is a relatively new affiliate institution of the university system, thus engaging itself in every opportunity to gather and apply knowledge for institutional success.

This year, LPU-Laguna is celebrating its 22nd founding anniversary as an affiliate school of the LPU system. The institution is still in its quest to generate much knowledge for its organizational effectiveness, storing, encapsulating, and sharing them with all organization members. As discussed, they will also submit themselves to a "university ship" through the Institutional Sustainability Assessment (ISA) to be conducted by CHED. A great deal of expertise in governance and management,

instruction and learning standards, professional exposure, research, and creative work standards, student assistance, and community connections will be needed for accreditation (CHED Memo no. 46 s. 2012). This quest for accreditation explains why the respondents from this campus have a more positive assessment of the knowledge generation, storage, and sharing phases of the knowledge management process.

As to age, responses vary on knowledge application, and these significant differences lie in those who are 31 to 40 years old. Mid-career faculty members fall within this age range (cupahr.org, 2020). The conclusion that middle-aged faculty members are more engaged in knowledge application than other age groups in the organization is not supported by any substantial studies. All knowledge workers have value and should be shared and protected, according to Prelog et al. (2019). Many mid-career faculty members are under pressure to mentor their students and their peers and impart their knowledge (Misra et al., 2016). Consequently, faculty members during these ages are more likely to divert their time and energy to figuring out how they will learn new knowledge and apply all the knowledge they have. Faculty members during these ages face the significant challenges of keeping their teaching fresh and keeping themselves engaged, enthusiastic, and instructional moving forward.

Lastly, there were significant differences in knowledge storage when grouped according to area of specialization and tenure. This was observed since the resulting p-values were less than the alpha level. Based on the post hoc test, it was found that those in culinary, tourism, and hospitality management and serving for 15 to 20 years better evaluate storage. Customer service is the hospitality industry's cornerstone; professionals and educators strive to give it superbly and accurately. Thus, especially for individuals who have worked in the field for a considerable amount of time, keeping knowledge, facts, and experiences on hand is essential for carrying out their tasks. They should have access to the more recent knowledge that the younger experts have to provide.

No significant evidence has shown the relevance of the culinary, tourism, and hospitality management field to the high assessment level of the knowledge storage phase of knowledge management. However, Batra (2022) highlighted the various types of knowledge available in the hospitality and tourism industries, such as task-specific knowledge, task-related knowledge, transactive memory, guest-related knowledge, customer/supplier-related knowledge, market-related knowledge, and network-related knowledge. Because of the fierce rivalry in the travel and tourism sector, businesses need to use knowledge management, particularly in storing them, and offer levels of customer care that are above and beyond the norm (Bloomfire, 2021).

These days, older workers may decide to work through retirement rather than leave the workforce altogether (Fisher et al., 2016; Sullivan et al., 2019; Wöhrmann et al., 2017). ALL personnel is not only permitted to keep enhancing their knowledge, abilities, and possibilities for innovation in a learning organization with KM systems in place but they are also encouraged to do so. As a result, it is essential to adopt inclusive KM in a workforce with a varied range of ages (Hill, 2021). Older coworkers are being forced by the development of ICT for knowledge management to emphasize the knowledge storage phase out of concern that they will not be able to take advantage of its advantages and benefits in knowledge storage. According to research, senior employees are the group that is least motivated to share knowledge (Bostjancic, 2019), making them dependent on the knowledge shared and kept by the younger employees (Fasbender et al., 2021).

Table 16. Difference of Responses on the Knowledge Management Process When Grouped According to Profile

Campus	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Knowledge Generation	2.597	0.037	Significant
Knowledge Storage	3.339	0.011	Significant
Knowledge Sharing	2.493	0.044	Significant
Knowledge Application	2.288	0.061	Not Significant
Age			
Knowledge Generation	1.293	0.268	Not Significant
Knowledge Storage	1.611	0.158	Not Significant
Knowledge Sharing	1.817	0.110	Not Significant
Knowledge Application	2.412	0.037	Significant
Gender			
Knowledge Generation	0.524	0.470	Not Significant
Knowledge Storage	0.036	0.851	Not Significant
Knowledge Sharing	0.089	0.766	Not Significant
Knowledge Application	0.730	0.394	Not Significant
Qualifications			
Knowledge Generation	0.882	0.415	Not Significant
Knowledge Storage	1.955	0.144	Not Significant
Knowledge Sharing	0.005	0.995	Not Significant
Knowledge Application	1.179	0.309	Not Significant
Area of Specialization			
Knowledge Generation	1.169	0.322	Not Significant
Knowledge Storage	2.246	0.032	Significant
Knowledge Sharing	1.306	0.248	Not Significant
Knowledge Application	1.190	0.310	Not Significant
Tenure Ship			
Knowledge Generation	1.301	0.270	Not Significant
Knowledge Storage	2.653	0.034	Significant
Knowledge Sharing	1.967	0.100	Not Significant
Knowledge Application	1.705	0.150	Not Significant

Table 17 compares responses on Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes when grouped according to profile. It was observed that there was a significant difference in research since the obtained p-value of 0.018 was less than the alpha level. This means that the responses differ statistically and shows that those who are in LPU-Laguna have better assessments than others. This is because LPU-Laguna is on the verge of generating as much knowledge as possible. It is good to know that all campus members know the institution's need to implement KM to ensure organizational success as an HEI.

LPU-Laguna is one of the newest campuses of the university system. It is an affiliated school of the LPU system and cannot consider itself a stand-alone "university." This campus must still submit to Institutional Sustainability Accreditation (ISA) by the Philippine Commission on Higher Education. According to CHED Memo No. 46 s. 2012, the Institutional Sustainability Assessment (ISA) is a quality assurance process that evaluates the institutional sustainability of an HEI in the critical areas of quality of teaching and learning as supported by governance and management, support for students, relationships with the community, and quality of exposure, research, and creative work.

The assessment system comprises five major result areas, including Quality of Professional Exposure, Research, and Creative Work, where institutions' performance is evaluated. This best describes the high assessment of the respondents from LPU-Laguna on research as they are gearing

toward ISA accreditation. Research is one of the core elements of the mission of a great university. Research must be conducted in a university because that is where higher education is delivered, where students gain breadth and depth of knowledge in fundamental and advanced subjects, and where the skills of knowledge acquisition and understanding (including contextualization, interpretation, and inference) are refined, and where students are educated, trained, and otherwise prepared for successful careers (Rosowsky, 2022).

Regarding age, responses vary on teaching ($p = 0.044$) and research ($p = 0.007$), and these significant differences lie in those who are 31 to 40 years old. This significant difference is a question between reluctance or willingness of senior / older employees to share the knowledge they have. Perhaps, senior faculty members are reluctant to share their knowledge with younger faculty members because of fear of tenure in the university system. Senior faculty members may feel that if they share their knowledge in teaching and research with younger ones, the management may consider employing them later.

All knowledge workers have value and should be shared and protected, according to Prelog et al. (2019). There is a significant positive relationship between knowledge level and age. According to a 2019 Bostjancic study, older workers are less inclined to impart their skills. According to Finkelstein et al. (2013), middle-aged workers may believe that younger workers are vying for their positions, which causes them to be more protective of their knowledge. Younger workers are more willing to share their knowledge since they need to learn a lot, and they anticipate that by doing so, other workers will do the same for them. Senior employees are the least motivated of all age groups, which has implications for workplace organizations because this age group has the most tacit knowledge—knowledge that is challenging to transmit and record—compared to other age groups. The only way for firms to keep this expertise is to impart it to younger staff. Thus, it is crucial that senior staff feel inspired to do so.

Moreover, there was also a significant difference in international outlook when grouped according to sex and area of specialization. Based on the post hoc test tested, it was found that females and those in culinary, tourism, and hospitality management have better observation than others. The hospitality industry is linked to internationalization and globalization; thus, hospitality professionals and educators are more particular about the importance of knowledge management to internationalization and how it can improve the outlook of an organization or an academic institution in the international arena.

No existing literature will support the findings of why female faculty members in the culinary, tourism, and hospitality management fields better observe the international outlook as a measure of performance outcome of knowledge management implementation in HEIs. Based in an interview with three (3) female faculty members in the culinary, tourism, and hospitality management field who are actual respondents of this study, they mentioned that particular importance to internationalization was highlighted through their responses because the nature of their profession is inclined with diversity, culture, traditions, service, and travel. The interviewees emphasized that though they are in the academe, they still want to incorporate the nature of their actual profession in the educational setup. This explains why their profession and gender significantly differ in the respective dimensions.

Table 17. Difference of Responses on the Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes When Grouped According to Profile

Campus	F-value	p-value	Interpretation
Teaching	2.040	0.090	Not Significant
Research	3.046	0.018	Significant
International Outlook	0.813	0.518	Not Significant
Age			
Teaching	2.325	0.044	Significant
Research	3.282	0.007	Significant
International Outlook	1.873	0.100	Not Significant
Gender			
Teaching	2.186	0.141	Not Significant
Research	0.232	0.630	Not Significant
International Outlook	8.292	0.004	Significant
Qualifications			
Teaching	0.301	0.740	Not Significant
Research	0.495	0.610	Not Significant
International Outlook	1.754	0.175	Not Significant
Area of Specialization			
Teaching	1.753	0.098	Not Significant
Research	0.956	0.464	Not Significant
International Outlook	2.230	0.033	Significant
Tenure Ship			
Teaching	1.573	0.182	Not Significant
Research	1.523	0.196	Not Significant
International Outlook	0.610	0.656	Not Significant

Table 18 illustrates the association between Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices and the KM Process. It was observed from the result that the computed R-values indicate a robust direct correlation, and the resulting p-values were less than the alpha level. This indicates a significant relationship and reveals that the more they practiced knowledge management, the better the knowledge management process.

The table presents Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices such as Organizational Culture, Information Technology, and Employee Motivation as independent variables while KM Process is the dependent variable. The level of KM Practices on KM Processes in terms of Knowledge Generation, Knowledge Storage, Knowledge Sharing, and Knowledge Application is significantly associated with the Key Factors of KM Practices such as Organizational Culture, Information Technology, and Employee Motivation. It can be inferred that the successful implementation of KM Practices is significant in improving the KM Process.

The results imply that Information Technology, based on R-values, has the most significant contribution to Knowledge Generation, Storage, Sharing, and Application. Information technology of the university system has a secured database, is managed by key experts, and has security protocols in place for data and knowledge management (4.67). This means that availability of IT facilitates knowledge sharing culture and provides easy access to information, facilitating better decision-making in all aspects of KM.

Organizational competitiveness can be attained (Sulisworo, 2012) due to the usage of information technology in Malaysia's public higher education institutions, which enables knowledge management activities such as knowledge capture, storage, and transfer (Ramachandran, 2013). Information technology is also crucial for managing knowledge. Information technology, however, does not affect knowledge management procedures, according to studies by Andreeva et al. (2012), Choi et al. (2012), and Davison et al. (2013).

Organizational Culture practices in terms of controlling the use of information in line with regulatory and compliance requirements (4.65); incorporating knowledge sharing in training and

developmental activities (4.64); and facilitating knowledge sharing signify good practices in knowledge generation, storage, sharing, and application.

The processes of creating, storing, sharing, and using information are all influenced by organizational culture (Lee et al., 2012; Omerzel et al., 2012; Rivera et al., 2016; Tan et al., 2013). The most critical component for enabling knowledge management processes has been identified as culture. Knowledge management will probably be better when corporate culture is applied (Fiscal, 2019). Studies, however, claim that culture does not affect how new knowledge is created and disseminated (Sunalai, 2015).

The results also imply that Employee Motivation, based on R-values, significantly contributes to Knowledge Generation, Storage, Sharing, and Application. Employee motivation is crucial for professors and staff since motivated employees perform better (Fiscal, 2021). Employee motivation is the term used to describe organizational benefits like bonuses and non-cash rewards like praise, promotions, and job stability. Furthermore, the university system has developed a specific set of indicators to manage knowledge (4.34), budget allocation (4.31), and measures set for Intellectual capital (4.25).

The results are consistent with the studies stating that organizational rewards were imperative to build a significant knowledge-sharing relationship (Tan et al., 2013) and used to encourage academic staff to share (Lin, 2017). Additionally, university reward programs can increase faculty members' efforts and involvement in knowledge sharing as well as have an impact on other students' commitment to sharing knowledge (Fiscal, 2019).

Table 18. Relationship Between Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices and Knowledge Management Process

Organizational Culture	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Knowledge Generation	0.639	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Storage	0.723	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Sharing	0.695	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Application	0.767	0.000	Highly Significant
Information Technology			
Knowledge Generation	0.771	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Storage	0.715	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Sharing	0.747	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Application	0.721	0.000	Highly Significant
Employee Motivation			
Knowledge Generation	0.475	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Storage	0.648	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Sharing	0.546	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Application	0.639	0.000	Highly Significant

Table 19 displays the association between Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices and Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes. Based on the result, the computed r-values indicate a robust direct correlation, and the resulting p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that a significant relationship exists and implies that the more they practiced knowledge management, the better the performance outcomes. The Key Factors of KM practices regarding Organizational Culture, Information Technology, and Employee Motivation are significantly associated with the Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes regarding teaching, research, and international outlook.

These findings imply that Organizational Culture ($r = 0.669$) significantly contributes to the university system's Teaching, Research, and International Outlook Performance Outcomes. In knowledge management and exchange, there is considerable disagreement regarding the place of culture in educational institutions (Lee et al., 2015; River et al., 2016; Sangjae et al., 2012). Knowledge sharing is influenced by organizational culture, among other things. According to Moorehead et al. (2015), academic members tend to hoard knowledge because the culture of higher education fosters factionalism and interpersonal hostilities. In order to gain a competitive edge and achieve organizational success, leaders of HEIs require a culture that promotes information sharing and knowledge retention (Muhammad, 2019). The most crucial factor for effective knowledge management

is culture. According to Gurbie et al. (2018), corporate culture encompasses all the principles and values that guide company behavior.

Furthermore, Organizational Culture practices in terms of controlling the use of information in line with regulatory and compliance requirements (4.65); incorporating knowledge sharing in training and developmental activities (4.64); and facilitating knowledge sharing signify good practices in knowledge generation, storage, sharing, and application and initiates excellent performance outcomes for KM implementation in the university system.

According to several research (Kanaan et al., 2013; Abualoush, 2018), knowledge sharing inside an organization is a process influenced by various elements, including the nature of the knowledge, employee attribute, nature of the organization, and employee attitude.

Employee motivation is the inner drive that propels a person to work harder toward personal and professional goals. The organizations will benefit from intense employee motivation. Additionally, highly productive personnel will contribute to the organization's productivity growth, raising it to new heights. According to research, motivated individuals perform at their highest level at work (Kanaan, 2019).

In this study, employee motivation is significantly associated with KM Performance Outcomes ($r = 0.601$). Furthermore, the university system has developed a specific set of indicators to manage knowledge (4.34), budget allocation (4.31), and measures set for Intellectual capital (4.25), which contribute to a high level of KM Performance Outcomes.

The results are consistent with the study's findings that employee involvement significantly and favorably affects organizational performance and knowledge sharing, further influencing organizational performance. Employee involvement and knowledge sharing may therefore be the most excellent way to address the existing issues with Knowledge Management adoption in organizations and sustain the organization's high performance (Ahmed, 2020).

In this study, Information Technology, based on R-values, is also significantly associated with KM performance Outcomes ($r = 0.598$). Information technology of the university system has a secured database, is managed by key experts, and has security protocols in place for data and knowledge management (4.67). This means that the availability of Information Technology systems contributes to high-performance outcomes for KM implementation in the university system.

The adoption and use of ICT to improve and facilitate Knowledge Management (KM) have highlighted the urgent need to develop new approaches, tools, and techniques in the creation of KM systems frameworks, knowledge processes, and knowledge technologies to promote effective management of knowledge for enhanced service delivery in higher education (Sulisworo, 2012). According to studies (Alfrouz, 2015; Lazic et al., 2021; Vyas, 2021; Sharma et al., 2018), information technology significantly affects the success of knowledge management procedures. Use of IT tools: According to Qazi et al. (2018), the impact of KM on organizational performance increases with increased tool and information quality, user happiness, utilization, and accessibility.

Table 19. Relationship Between Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices and Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes

Organizational Culture	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Teaching	0.766	0.000	Highly Significant
Research	0.549	0.000	Highly Significant
International Outlook	0.691	0.000	Highly Significant
Information Technology			
Teaching	0.669	0.000	Highly Significant
Research	0.676	0.000	Highly Significant
International Outlook	0.448	0.000	Highly Significant
Employee Motivation			
Teaching	0.682	0.000	Highly Significant
Research	0.400	0.000	Highly Significant
International Outlook	0.722	0.000	Highly Significant

Table 20 presents the association between Knowledge Management Processes and Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes. Based on the result, the computed r-values indicate a robust direct correlation, and the resulting p-values were less than the alpha level. This means that there was a

significant relationship between the two variables. Thus, the result shows that the better the knowledge management processes, the better the performance outcomes. The level of KM Performance Outcomes in terms of Teaching, Research, and International Outlook is significantly associated with Knowledge Generation, Storage, Sharing, and Application.

These findings imply that Knowledge Application ($r = 0.756$) significantly contributes to Teaching, Research, and International Outlook Performance Outcomes. Knowledge Application refers to the application of different best practices in the teaching and learning process and research and utilization of different technology to develop new knowledge. Furthermore, the university system utilizes knowledge embedded in procedures, rules, norms, and processes that guide future behavior (4.55), has best practices in the educational process (4.53), applies knowledge to critical competitive needs, and quickly links sources of knowledge in problem-solving (4.51). The findings are consistent with the result of the study conducted by Fiscal (2019), wherein Knowledge Application also has the most significant contribution to the success of KM in state universities in the Philippines.

The outcome is also in line with a study by Ngoc-Tan et al. (2018), which found that innovation was positively predicted by knowledge generation (knowledge creation), knowledge dissemination (knowledge sharing), and responsiveness to knowledge (knowledge application). The ability to do all three knowledge processes makes an organization more innovative.

Knowledge sharing is one of the fundamental tools an organization can use to foster innovation and advance scientific research (Al Hussein et al., 2012; Mohammed et al., 2014). This study's knowledge management performance outcomes are significantly associated with knowledge sharing ($r = 0.752$). University libraries and resource centers to display and disseminate knowledge (4.64); regular symposiums, lectures, conferences, and teaching and training sessions (4.58); and participation in multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and discipline-based research projects (4.55) link the knowledge management performance outcomes of the university system.

Moreover, the KM Performance Outcomes are also significantly associated with Knowledge Generation ($r = 0.716$) and Knowledge Storage ($r = 0.705$). This means utilizing databases, repositories, and information technology applications to store knowledge for easy access by all academics (4.49); storing knowledge / archiving the content and implementation of the educational process (4.48); and utilizing various written devices such as newsletters manuals to store knowledge captured from academics (4.48) facilitates storing knowledge in the university system. Similarly, Knowledge Generation in terms of employing mechanisms for acquiring research knowledge from different sources such as academics, CHED, industries, and competitors (4.65), encouraging the creation of its own Research and Development centers by its faculty and staff (4.64); and encouraging and supporting faculty and staff to pursue graduate studies (4.64) initiates good knowledge management performance outcomes.

The findings also corresponded with Fiscal (2019), claiming that knowledge storage significantly improved university performance, particularly in teaching and learning.

Furthermore, Ohioenoya et al. (2014) and Naser et al. (2016) claimed that supporting knowledge management processes (creating knowledge, capturing knowledge, organizing knowledge, storing knowledge, disseminating knowledge, and applying knowledge) will significantly improve the university's performance in innovation, growth, and competitive advantage.

Similarly, Ramachandran et al. (2013) claimed that in order to achieve the desired performance outcomes, such as improved decision-making, staff, and student handling, improved employee skills, productivity, communication, innovation and creativity, learning/adaptation capability, higher education institutions needed to give equal attention to all knowledge management processes (processes of creating, gathering, organizing, storing, diffusing, use, and exploitation of knowledge). Additionally, knowledge management practices benefit organizational performance regarding collaboration, human capital, and research innovation (Rasula et al., 2012; Paez-Logreira et al., 2016).

Table 20. Relationship Between Knowledge Management Process and Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes

Knowledge Generation	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Teaching	0.736	0.000	Highly Significant
Research	0.835	0.000	Highly Significant
International Outlook	0.576	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Storage			
Teaching	0.774	0.000	Highly Significant
Research	0.727	0.000	Highly Significant
International Outlook	0.615	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Sharing			
Teaching	0.816	0.000	Highly Significant
Research	0.830	0.000	Highly Significant
International Outlook	0.611	0.000	Highly Significant
Knowledge Application			
Teaching	0.833	0.000	Significant
Research	0.772	0.000	Significant
International Outlook	0.662	0.000	Significant

A regression test was run to predict the Key Factors of KM Practices and KM Processes from KM Performance Outcomes. The model equation result is $KMO = -0.102 + KMP (0.294) + KMS (0.711)$. These variables statistically significantly predicted Key Factors of KM Practices and KM Process $F_{(2, 233)} = 492.751, p < 0.001, r^2 = 0.809$. Upon further scrutiny of the data, all KM variables added statistically significantly to the prediction, $p < 0.001$. The test revealed that KMP and KMS were significant predictors of KMO. The test also shows that KM practices regarding KM implementation are more important (0.711). Thus, the university system must give more importance to intensifying the implementation of practices related to Knowledge Management.

Table 21. Predictors of Knowledge Management Performance Outcomes

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.102	.145		-.703	.482
	KM Process (KMP)	.294	.052	.283	5.655	<.001
	KM Practices (KMS)	.711	.055	.652	13.023	<.001

$F_{(2, 233)} = 492.751, p < 0.001, r^2 = 0.809$

To present the significant relationships between the variables, the following statements describe their association. Organizational culture will correlate positively and significantly with knowledge generation, storage, sharing, and application. Further, Information Technology will correlate positively and significantly with knowledge generation, storage, sharing, and application. Also, Employee Motivation will correlate positively and significantly with knowledge generation, storage, knowledge sharing, and application.

Moreover, the Knowledge Generation stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes. Also, the Knowledge Storage stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes. Knowledge Sharing stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes. Furthermore, the Knowledge Application stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes.

Figure 1. Proposed Knowledge Management Model

This proposed Knowledge Management Model is composed of the three (3) main variables of the study, Key Factors of KM Practices, KM Processes, and KM Performance Outcomes and their respective dimensions. The model presents the significant relationships and associations of KM Practices and Processes to the Performance Outcomes of KM implementation.

The presented model is based on the assessment result of the current practices and processes implemented in the university system and its performance outcomes. Hence, this model can serve as a basis for guiding the university system in implementing its future knowledge management initiatives. It can also serve as a foundation for future empirical studies to help understand existing knowledge management practices and identify gaps needed for university improvements. This proposed model is also based on an existing model of Knowledge Management in Nigerian Universities (Ojo, 2016) and Higher Education Institutions in Thailand (Sunalai, 2015). The scarcity of studies investigating knowledge management initiatives or practices in the context of universities in the Philippines is a limitation worth acknowledging.

To present the significant relationships between the variables, the following statements describe their association. Organizational culture will correlate positively and significantly with knowledge generation, storage, sharing, and application. Further, Information Technology will correlate positively and significantly with knowledge generation, storage, sharing, and application. Also, Employee Motivation will correlate positively and significantly with knowledge generation, storage, knowledge sharing, and application.

Moreover, the Knowledge Generation stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes. Also, the Knowledge Storage stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes. Knowledge Sharing stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes. Furthermore, the Knowledge Application stage will correlate positively and significantly with the quality of Performance Outcomes.

The first stage in the Knowledge Management Process is Knowledge Generation. Based on the study's results, knowledge generation is always practiced by the university system (4.52). The results of the assessment of the implementation of Knowledge Generation have shown that the university system has mechanisms for acquiring knowledge from external sources (4.65); collaborates in joint projects (4.64); encourages R&D among its faculty members (4.64); and supports faculty and staff to enroll post-graduate studies (4.64). However, the university system needs to have well-established research programs and activities for the faculty members (4.61); and invite world-known lecturers to share knowledge (4.51).

The university system must define its knowledge needs and obtain the necessary knowledge. Knowledge generation is essential for institutions using their knowledge assets for problem-solving, strategic planning, curriculum development, and general repositioning. Being in the knowledge

industry, universities should be able to recognize their current knowledge assets and produce new information as needed. Knowledge mapping is compared to knowledge generation, which measures the institution's intellectual capital by visualizing knowledge assets to understand how, when, and where to access knowledge. By carrying out such a procedure, the university system would be able to identify its core capabilities, ensure better resource allocation, spot potential synergies, and achieve its objectives. Network analysis, benchmarking trips, and brainstorming meetings are other ways to generate knowledge, mainly to capture tacit knowledge. This can aid in creating knowledge at the departmental and faculty levels, which can subsequently be incorporated into a knowledge repository for the entire university.

The second stage is knowledge storage. Based on the study's results, Knowledge storage is often practiced (4.45) by the university system. Results also have shown that the university system utilizes databases, repositories, and information technology applications to store knowledge (4.49), has an archive for the implementation of educational processes (4.48), and utilizes written devices to store knowledge (4.48). There is a need for the university system to strengthen the implementation of the activities and practices related to storing knowledge to ensure a more effective and efficient performance outcome.

Owning a knowledge repository that can be consulted when necessary is the essence of knowledge identification. Once knowledge has been located and compiled, it must be kept in a repository. In a university setting, however, there is a requirement for a repository of academic and administrative operations in addition to a repository including topic experts by their specialty. A knowledge repository system that serves as an organizational knowledge base will make it easier to implement knowledge activities, including knowledge capture, information exchange, and knowledge discovery. A knowledge repository also serves as the organization's memory, storing information incorporated into a system, including customs, history, business procedures, and human expertise. Knowledge storage enables establishing an organizational memory of internal knowledge that has been amassed over time. Thus, knowledge storage enables businesses to reuse knowledge as needed, resulting in time and cost savings that could increase performance.

Knowledge sharing is the third stage. The university system must work to disseminate knowledge stored in repositories, or its teachers and staff possess that at this level. Information sharing is essential to knowledge management operations as a prerequisite to knowledge application or usage. Based on the study's results, knowledge sharing is always practiced in the university system (4.53). The results also showed that the university system has libraries and resource centers to share knowledge (4.64); has regular symposia, conferences, and teaching and training sessions to share knowledge (4.58), and supports the participation of employees to research projects (4.55). However, there is a need to intensify its awareness campaign on research projects among young academicians (4.47); and should have an efficient coaching and mentoring system (4.46).

Knowledge application is the fourth stage. Based on the study's results, the knowledge application process is often practiced in the university system (4.49). Though the university system utilizes knowledge embedded in its procedures and processes (4.55); applies best practices in the educational processes (4.53); and applies knowledge in problem-solving (4.51), there is a solid need to devise methods for the employees to develop and apply the knowledge they have in new situations (4.46), and makes use of the available disposable intellectual potential (4.44). The university system must use the learned information to increase productivity and creativity if knowledge management activities are beneficial. Knowledge management must be used for academic and administrative activities to offer the university system a competitive edge. According to academics, universities should use knowledge management to enhance teaching, learning, and research processes, establish new academic programs, strengthen existing curricula, enhance student and alumni services, develop strategic plans and policies, and improve overall service delivery. Knowledge flow is the total amount of knowledge and know-how exchanged over a specific period. According to this definition, the current study incorporates knowledge sharing and application into knowledge flow because each has to do with the sharing and applying knowledge, and knowledge flow is the use of knowledge.

Knowledge management, knowledge production, and knowledge sharing in HEIs have been considered enabled by the information technology that supports and enables KM strategies and operations. Therefore, the university system must have access to cutting-edge ICT for a top-notch procedure for generating and creating knowledge.

It is believed that incentives and rewards are essential behavioral motivators. Universities must ensure that incentives acknowledge academicians' contributions to any system of knowledge creation and meet their expectations of successful results of knowledge sharing and creation, both in terms of extrinsic rewards and the fostering of relationships. Academics anticipate that their

involvement in knowledge management will strengthen and widen their ties to one another, provide chances for internal advancement, and advance their professional careers.

If workers believe that reliable and secure platforms and technologies exist for knowledge storage, they will be more inclined to store their collective knowledge. A company's culture plays a crucial role in the success of information sharing. He added that the organizational culture is considerably more robust than a faculty member's, regardless of how powerful their devotion and method of knowledge sharing may be.

The administration of the university system should foster a cooperative environment that encourages knowledge sharing among staff members. Leaders must design workplaces that encourage knowledge exchange. In order to prepare to capture those employees' expertise before they leave the organization, leaders must be aware of when their staff plan to retire and who may leave for other reasons. A knowledge-sharing culture also encourages employees to ask questions when they do not know something, which improves faculty morale and aids in the achievement of institutional goals and objectives.

This model is proposed to guide the university system's knowledge management efforts and initiatives. However, it is vital to remember that each process emphasized in the model has several enablers and drivers. A knowledge management system in a higher education setting must use the institution's people, procedures, technologies, and organizational structure to promote best practices and identify what functions well. Successful knowledge management programs require several critical elements, including a culture of information sharing, a reward system, and a culture that encourages information-based decision-making. By being aware of crucial domains in the context of higher education, HEIs may boost knowledge management methods. These areas include measurement, corporate culture, information technology, human resource management, and leadership. According to the premise, the university system must put leaders in positions where they can support the knowledge management process, foster an organizational culture that encourages knowledge sharing, and use information technology tools. Before executing knowledge management efforts, HEIs should complete a readiness assessment.

CONCLUSION

Critical Factors of Knowledge Management Practices such as Organizational Culture, Information Technology, and Employee Motivation got a high level of assessment as all the university system campuses are always practicing them.

Knowledge Management Process stages such as Knowledge Generation and Knowledge Sharing got a high level of assessment as all university system campuses are always practicing them. In contrast, Knowledge Storage and Knowledge Application stages got a moderate level of assessment as they are often practiced in the university system.

The performance outcomes for implementing Knowledge Management Practices and Knowledge Management Processes regarding teaching, research, and international outlook are moderately felt and observed at the university system.

A significant relationship exists between Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices and Knowledge Management Process, Key Factors of Knowledge Management Practices to KM Performance Outcomes, and KM Process and KM Performance Outcomes.

Important data about the current situation regarding implementing Knowledge Management in the university system was used to develop a Knowledge Management Model for the university system.

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